

BraTS 2026 Cluster of Challenges: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

BraTS 2026 Cluster of Challenges

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

BraTS

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The BraTS 2026 Cluster of Challenges is a multi-society multi-institutional collaborative effort, including the "Response Assessment in Neuro-Oncology" (RANO) cooperative group, leading clinical societies (RSNA, ASNR, ASFNR, ESNR, CBTN), and the NIH. Their partnership through BraTS aims to establish and promote clinically relevant challenges to maximize the potential clinical neuro-oncology impact of innovative algorithmic contributions from participating teams.

Since its inception at MICCAI 2012, BraTS has advanced brain glioma segmentation by enabling and benchmarking algorithmic developments, providing high-quality annotated datasets. In 2023, BraTS expanded to include multiple benchmarks, quantifying tumors beyond glioma (i.e., brain metastases, meningiomas, pediatric brain tumors, and sub-Saharan patient populations), histology image classification, and image synthesis. This novel, innovative design creates a benchmarking ecosystem for the systematic comparison of algorithms across diverse tasks and clinical challenges. In 2025, the BraTS Cluster of Challenges was conducted as one of the MICCAI Lighthouse challenges and during its concluding remarks reported that a few of its 11 challenges are considered solved problems – i.e., AI models reached the threshold of human expert inter-/intra-rater variability, as determined in an extensive re-annotation study for BraTS 2025 to quantify expert variance.

The significance of BraTS 2026 lies in its focus to address the challenges that remain unsolved and represent actual clinical needs across brain tumors, spanning i) tumor entities (for which there is currently limited publicly available annotated data), ii) clinical domains (radiology & pathology), iii) appearance differences (pre- and post-treatment settings), iii) & iv) computational workloads (e.g., segmentation, classification, synthesis). Corroborating BraTS' goal to address clinical needs, authoritative and leading federal and clinical organizations have partnered with BraTS (incl. NIH, RANO, RSNA, ASNR, ASFNR, CBTN).

Specifically, the BraTS 2026 Cluster of Challenges will encompass 5 MICCAI challenges, designed to benchmark

and advance the current state-of-the-art algorithms for addressing:

- (Challenge 1) Segmentation of brain metastases sub-regions in pre- and post-treatment MRI scans,
- (Challenge 2) Segmentation of pediatric brain tumor sub-regions in pre- and post-treatment MRI scans,
- (Challenge 3) Generalizability of brain tumor sub-region segmentation across tumor entities in MRI scans,
- (Challenge 4) Local Synthesis / Inpainting of brain tumor MRI scans,
- (Challenge 5) Classification of brain glioblastoma sub-regions in H&E-stained; pathology slides.

Participants will be able to obtain the training and validation data of the challenge at any point from the Synapse platform. To ensure accurate performance evaluation, expert neuroradiologists and neuropathologists have created and approved reference standard annotations for all datasets for each subject in the training, validation, and testing datasets.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

BraTS, Brain Tumors, Brain Tumor Sub-regions, Radiology, Pathology, Segmentation, Classification, Synthesis, Inpainting, Infill, Metastasis, Pediatrics, Glioblastoma

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

Across Challenges/Tasks (1-5):

When compared with previous iterations of BraTS challenges, this year we will provide additional non-annotated training data to the participants to enable innovations in semi-supervised learning methods.

Challenge/Task 1-3 (Metastasis, Pediatrics, Generalizability):

For the segmentation challenges, we will add a detection leaderboard, with the intention of promoting algorithms sensitive in detecting lesions. This is clinically relevant to cases of small (<27mm³) lesions that either need to be counted as separate entities, or that they need to be quantified separately.

Challenge/Task 1 (Metastasis):

In the metastasis challenge, we will perform an additional round of revising all annotations, to ensure the highest quality of the dataset.

Challenge/Task 2 (Pediatrics):

Prior BraTS pediatric segmentation challenges focused exclusively on treatment-naïve imaging. In the 2026 BraTS-PEDs challenge, we introduce a longitudinal post-treatment cohort comprising at least 105 post-treatment MRI cases. This addition enables, for the first time in a pediatric benchmark setting, systematic evaluation of segmentation robustness under therapy-induced changes, such as necrosis, resection cavities, and changing enhancement patterns, which are critical conditions that reflect real-world clinical deployment.

Challenge/Task 4 (Inpainting):

Building on the success of the past three years, the BraTS-Inpainting challenge remains dedicated to local MR infilling, an unresolved problem that continues to see strong community engagement. This year, we maintain our established focus on reconstructing anatomically plausible tissue within expert-verified masks across multi-institutional cohorts. To further align with real-world clinical needs, we are introducing experimental metrics based on grey- and white-matter segmentation performance to evaluate how well inpainted regions support downstream anatomical analysis and, thereby, develop application-specific metrics that go beyond existing image metrics such as SSIM or MAE.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The BraTS 2026 Cluster of Challenges will encompass 5 MICCAI challenges/tasks, designed to benchmark and advance the current state-of-the-art algorithms for addressing:

- (Challenge/Task 1) Segmentation of brain metastases sub-regions in pre-operative and post-treatment brain multi-parametric structural MRI scans of adult patients,
- (Challenge/Task 2) Segmentation of pediatric brain tumor sub-regions in pre-operative and post-treatment brain multi-parametric structural MRI scans of pediatric patients,
- (Challenge/Task 3) Generalizability of brain tumor sub-region segmentation algorithms across tumor entities and appearances in pre-operative brain multi-parametric structural MRI scans of both adult and pediatric patients. The distinct tumor entities considered include glioma, intracranial meningioma, brain metastases, and pediatric high grade glioma. The distinct appearances refer to data cohorts of both adult and pediatric patients from sub-Saharan Africa that due to socio-economic factors the pre-operative brain multi-parametric structural MRI scans have different appearance, as well as the tumors are imaged at a later stage of disease.
- (Challenge/Task 4) Local Synthesis / Inpainting of brain tumor multi-parametric structural MRI scans.
- (Challenge/Task 5) Classification of nine distinct brain glioblastoma morphologic sub-regions in H&E-stained; digitized tissue sections.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS**Workshop**

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

We intend to run BraTS 2026, in coordination with the Brain Abnormality Workshop (BrainWorks).

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

We ask for a half-day events (i.e., 4 hours) accounting for 45' per challenge. This allows very systematic challenge sessions including intro of each challenge and findings (10'), presentation of top-ranked methods (30'), and winner announcements (5').

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

For this year's cluster of challenges, we conservatively estimate 1,500 participating teams and 100 on-site attendees.

This is based on the continuously increasing number of teams participating in the BraTS challenge during its prior instances (2025:n=1,892, 2024:n=1,734, 2023:n=1,747, 2022:n=1,121, 2021: n>1,000).

We note a tremendous increase in participation and attendance, following the partnership with other societies, when compared with BraTS challenges prior to 2021, i.e., 2020: n=78, 2019: n=72, 2018: n=63, 2017: n=53, 2016: n=19, 2015: n=12, 2014: n=10, 2013: n=10, 2012:n=10. We strongly believe that the 2021 participation increase was a result of multiple factors (challenge maturity, involvement of RSNA & ASNR, professional evaluation through Synapse and Kaggle) that has been carried forward since 2021 up to this year's cluster of challenges, thereby guaranteeing broad participation.

We also advertise the event in related mailing lists (e.g., CVML; visionlist@visionscience.com; cvnet@mail.ewind.com; MIPS@LISTSERV.CC.EMORY.EDU), NCI's CBIIT blog posts and tweets, "Data Science Nigeria" (DSN, <https://www.datasciencenigeria.org>), the "African Institute of Mathematical Sciences" (<https://aims.edu.gh>), the "African Centre of Excellence in Data Science" (ACE-DS, <https://aceds.ur.ac.rw/>), and the "INDABA" (<https://deeplearningindaba.com>), and we intend to send an email to all the above registered teams and notify them about this year's challenge.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We intend to coordinate 2 specific publication plans for BraTS 2026.

Plan 1:

Coordination of the BraTS proceedings as part of the MICCAI Satellite Event proceedings, allowing the BraTS participants to publish their methods in the associated MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings. We have already been doing this for BraTS since 2015. This year we will have the BraTS proceedings as part of the main MICCAI Satellite Event proceedings.

Plan 2:

We coordinate post-conference meta-analysis journal manuscripts for each BraTS 2026 challenge, to inform the community about the obtained results, findings, and insights.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team (miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Hardware requirements for the in-person meeting: 1 projector, 2 microphones, loudspeakers

BraTS 2026 Cluster of Challenges describes off-site challenges, where 1) during the training phase, algorithms are trained using the participants' computing infrastructure, and 2) during the validation and final testing/ranking phase using the organizers' infrastructure (i.e., Synapse.org - SAGE Bionetworks).

TASK 1: BraTS-METS: Segmentation of brain metastases sub-regions in pre- and post-treatment MRI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Impact: Brain metastases are the most common CNS malignancy in adults, and evaluation of brain metastases in clinical practice is commonly limited to comparison to one prior imaging study due to the common presentation of multiple metastases in a single patient. Detailed analysis of multiple patient lesions on multiple serial scans is impossible in current clinical practice because of the time it requires to assess a study. Therefore, the development of automated segmentation tools for brain metastases is critical for providing precision-based patient care. In addition, accurate detection of small metastatic lesions that are smaller than 10 mm in diameter and are an average of 1-2 mm is critical for patient prognosis. Missing even a single lesion can result in the patient requiring repeat interventions and experience delays in treatment. In addition, gross total volume of brain metastases in a patient is an important predictor of patient outcomes and is not currently available in clinical practice due to the lack of volumetric segmentation tools that can be translated. Therefore, it is critical to develop novel segmentation algorithms for small brain metastases that detect and accurately volumetrically segment all lesions in pre-treatment and post-treatment settings, which is different from the initial 2023 edition of the challenge that was solely focused on pre-treatment segmentations. In BraTS 2026 Challenge, we are planning multiple additions. For lesions less than 5 mm in diameter, we plan to add a detection arm of the challenge and exclude these lesions from segmentation metrics. Many of the algorithms that were developed for gliomas, such as nnU-Net, demonstrate high dice scores for larger metastases, but their performance significantly drops off for small metastases. In clinical practice, detection of small metastases is more important than correct segmentation of their borders, therefore metastases smaller than 5 mm in diameter will be included only in the detection portion of the challenge. Additional review of the reference standard will also be performed based on running top performing algorithms and checking the erroneous cases. New annotation of image artifacts will also be performed to reduce the false positives. We also plan on adding a large longitudinal post-treatment cohort of imaging studies that includes post-radiation and post-surgical cases. This challenge will be critical for the development of novel segmentation and detection algorithms for brain metastases that are common in clinical practice and will provide algorithms that can be readily translated into clinical practice.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Segmentation, detection, small lesions, brain metastasis, pre-treatment, post-treatment, contrast-enhancing lesion, peritumoral edema, MRI, MICCAI

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Mariam Aboian, M.D., Ph.D. [Lead Organizer]

Children's Hospital of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, PA, USA

Nikolay Y. Yordanov, MD [Trainee Lead]

Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment in Neurology and Psychiatry, Sofia, Bulgaria

Spyridon Bakas, PhD,

Indiana University

Mehdi Astaraki, PhD,

Karolinska Institute

Nazanin Maleki, MD,

Children's Hospital of Philadelphia

Ahmed Moawad, MD,

Mercy Catholic Medical Center

Raisa Amiruddin, MBBS,

Children's Hospital of Philadelphia

Crystal Chukwurah,

Yale School of Medicine

Fabian Umeh,

Teesside University

Satrajit Chakrabarty,

Washington University

Maria Correia de Verdier, MD PhD,

Uppsala University

Jeffrey Rudie MD PhD,

University of California, San Diego

Nourel Hoda Tahon, MD Msc,

University of Missouri

Ayman Nada MD PhD,

University of Missouri

Yury Velichko PhD,

Northwestern University

Ayda Youssef, MD,
National Cancer Institute

Monika Pylarz,
Sano Centre for Computational Neuroscience

Marina Ivory,
King's College London

Gian Marco Conte, MD PhD,
Mayo Clinic

Fatima Memon MD, MPH,
Medical University of South Carolina

Florian Kofler, PhD,
Hertie Institute for AI in Brain Health

Ujjwal Baid, PhD
Emory University

Elizabeth Schrickel MD, PhD,
Ohio State University

Sanjay Aneja, MD,
Yale School of Medicine

Ajay Malhotra, MD,
Yale School of Medicine

Philipp Vollmuth, MD, PhD,
University of Bonn

Keyvan Farahani, PhD,
National Institutes of Health

Matthew W. Pease, MD
Indiana University School of Medicine

Scott Floyd, MD, PhD,
Duke University

Verena Chung,
Sage Bionetworks

Devon Godfrey, PhD
Duke University Medical Center

The trainee annotator group is continuously growing, currently encompassing around 150 individuals from over 15 countries. These trainees have various backgrounds, including medical students in the latter stages of their education, radiology residents, and researchers. To ensure high-quality annotations, each one undergoes thorough training before beginning the actual annotation.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Mariam Aboian, MD PhD
Children's Hospital of Philadelphia
mariam.aboian@gmail.com

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Their role is to contribute with their clinical knowledge and expertise from practice to increase the clinical relevance and integrability of the algorithms produced during the challenge. The clinicians approve of the quality of the training, validation and testing datasets used for the challenge.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline, and continuous evaluation after the conference deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Synapse.org

Following our successful collaboration with the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks) since the RSNA-ASNR-MICCAI BraTS 2021 challenge, we have coordinated with them and following the support from NCI (represented by Dr Keyvan Farahani in the organizing committee - Chair of the NCI AI Challenges Working Group) Synapse will be used as the platform to drive the evaluation of this cluster of challenges.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS 2026 challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in a number of ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long-time co-organizer of BraTS challenges and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC). All aforementioned NCI platforms are implemented on the Google Cloud Platform. This collaboration with Synapse, enabled by NCI/NIH support through ITCR grant (Synapse, PI) and other NCI resources represents a major advancement in the challenge design and leveraging of public resources.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026> - (Website will be publicly visible after the challenge approval)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

We are seeking the development of automated algorithms.

Participants must submit a fully automated container that no user interaction is required for successful execution.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples), as long as it does not involve resources unavailable to other participants. Example of such resources are: proprietary software, clinical expertise to create additional reference standard annotations.

Our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods. Thus, if participants have a solution that includes any resources unavailable to other participants, they are allowed to submit it, but if they do so, they MUST also submit a solution that does not include these resources and discuss the potential difference in their results between the two solutions.

We urge participants to coordinate with the organizers if there is any clarification required.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

All participants are allowed to use publicly available pre-trained models (e.g., foundation models), as well as additional data from datasets publicly available at the time of the challenge launch.

Since our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods, participating teams are allowed to even use data from their own institutions (unavailable to other participants) for further complementing the data, but if they do so, they MUST also discuss the potential difference in their results before and after using these “private” data.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but organizers and their immediate groups cannot be 1) eligible for awards, 2) announced as the winners of the challenge, or 3) included in the announced formal rankings. They will however be evaluated and if they are within the top-ranked ones they will be honorarily mentioned to contribute back to the community. Since organizing institutions are large, other employees from other labs/departments may participate and should be eligible for the awards and to be listed in the official leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge organizers are in communication with industrial partners and MICCAI SIGs, to sponsor monetary awards for the top 3 teams. Formal confirmation can only be provided after the acceptance of the challenge. Note that the organizers have been securing monetary awards during each of BraTS 2018-2025. NIH will also provide Certificates of Merit to the top 3 performing teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly at the conference and the participants will be invited to present their method during an oral presentation.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

We intend to coordinate 2 specific publication plans for BraTS 2026.

Plan 1:

Coordination of the BraTS proceedings as part of the MICCAI Satellite Event proceedings, allowing the BraTS participants to publish their methods in the associated MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings. We have already been publishing BraTS Springer proceedings since 2015. This year we will have the BraTS proceedings as part of the main MICCAI Satellite Event Springer LNCS proceedings.

Plan 2:

We coordinate a post-conference meta-analysis journal manuscript to summarize the results, findings, and insights of the 2026 challenge.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The participants are required to send the output of their methods to the evaluation platform for the scoring to occur during the training and the validation phases. At the end of the validation phase the participants are asked to identify the method they would like to evaluate in the final testing/ranking phase.

The organizers will then confirm receiving the containerized method and will evaluate it in the hidden testing data. The participants will be provided guidelines on the form of the container as we have done in previous years. This will enable confirmation of reproducibility.

During the training and validation phases, the participants will have the chance to test the functionality of their submission through both the implementation of the evaluation metrics (provided at the challenge website), as well as via the online evaluation platform (Synapse).

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We intend to publicly release the training and the validation sets, as soon as the challenge is approved but not later than April 2026, allowing participants to train and tune their methods. The validation data ground truth will not be provided to the participants, but multiple submissions to the online evaluation platform will be allowed for the validation phase. However, only 2 submissions will be allowed in the final testing/ranking data/phase to avoid potential tuning of the submitted approach to the testing data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period

- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration dates: From website opening until submission deadline of short papers reporting method and preliminary results (see below).

16 March 2026 (or earlier): Registration opens – Release of Training and Validation data

Participants will be able to register for the challenge in synapse.org, from the date of its potential acceptance (either Feb 9, or Mar 16, 2026) until the short paper submission deadline (July 31, 2026).

Availability of training data (with ground truth labels) and validation data (without ground truth labels).

31 July 2026: Submission deadline for Paper and Containerized method

Paper should include motivation, literature, method description, and results on training and validation data.

The containerized method will be evaluated on the hidden testing data by the organizers, only for participants with submitted short papers. Ranking of all participating methods, following statistical significance assessment based on multiple permutation testing.

7 August 2026: Initial invitations are sent

Inviting participants with a valid submitted paper and an evaluated container to present at the conference (type of presentation will be determined within the next 2 weeks)

14 August 2026: Paper reviews are available

19 August 2026: Release of summary testing results to each participant.

Participants will receive summary testing data results, in order to report those in their papers.

21 August 2026: Camera-ready paper and Copyright form submission deadline

24 August 2026: Contacting top-performing methods for preparing slides for oral presentation.

1 September 2026: Organizers to send all proceedings material to the MICCAI 2026 Satellite Event committee for inclusion in the MICCAI LNCS Springer Proceedings.

4-8 October 2026: Challenge at MICCAI

Announcement of final top 3 ranked teams

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The Longitudinal Yale Dataset is currently publicly available on TCIA: DOI: 10.7937/3yat-e768, arXiv:2506.14021v1

We are in close coordination with The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA) and the Imaging Data Commons (IDC) of the National Institutes of Health (NIH), to release the training and validation data following their standard licensing (<https://wiki.cancerimagingarchive.net/display/Public/Data+Usage+Policies+and+Restrictions>). The TCIA has already approved this, and we are now in the process of submission (includes a detailed curation process specific to TCIA). The cloud-based IDC is routinely updated with new collections from TCIA. IDC public collections are now part of the Google Public Datasets Program. This will effectively make all the BraTS data available in the Google Marketplace, increasing the potential for access to the data and downstream AI developments using Google's AI resources. IDC data are also expected to be available through the AWS (Amazon Web Services) Marketplace.

Informed consent was obtained from all subjects at their respective institutions, and the protocol for releasing the data was approved by the institutional review board of the data-contributing institution.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY (Attribution)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The implementation and references to the pre-processing tools, exact evaluation metrics, and the ranking code used during the whole challenge's lifecycle will be made available through the challenge's website (<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants are required to submit their containerized algorithm, during or after the validation phase. Specific instructions for the containerization will be provided after the challenge approval. These instructions will be very similar to what we were requesting participants to provide during the BraTS 2021-2025 challenges.

All challenge participants will be required to accept an agreement through the synapse.org website that participation in the testing phase of the challenge, will automatically mean that we can make their containerized method publicly available through our challenge webpage and a collective toolkit we are putting together.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in several ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long time co-organizer of BraTS challenges and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC) on the Google Cloud Platform

The organizers are in coordination with industrial collaborators to offer dissemination of top-ranked containerized methods for research use only, through their commercial platforms, subject to participating teams accepting this opportunity.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Mariam Aboian, MD PhD, Spyridon Bakas, Ujjwal Baid, SAGE Bionetworks, and the clinical evaluators will have access to the validation, and test case labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training

- Cross-phase

Research, CAD, Decision support, Treatment planning, Diagnosis, Assistance, Surgery, Intervention planning, Education, Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Detection

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Adult brain metastasis patients

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Retrospective multi-institutional cohort of patients, diagnosed with metastasis, clinically scanned with mpMRI acquisition protocol during pre-treatment and post-treatment including i) pre-contrast and ii) contrast-enhanced T1-weighted, iii) T2-weighted and iv) T2-weighted Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) MRI.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Multi-parametric MRI scans of the brain, including T1-weighted, T2-weighted, FLAIR T2, and contrast-enhanced T1-weighted images.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information pertains directly to the image data (i.e., Tumor sub-region labels and volumes)

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

N/A

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain mpMRI scans in patients with brain metastases before and after initiation of treatment.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with brain tumors, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Sensitivity, Specificity, Dice, Normalized Surface Distance

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The exact scanners and their technical specifications used for acquiring the TCIA cohort have been listed in the data reference published in our related manuscripts. Since then, multiple institutions have contributed data to create the current BraTS 2023-26 Metastasis dataset and these will be listed in the latest BraTS arXiv paper

following acceptance of the challenge. We are currently in coordination with TCIA to make the complete BraTS 2023-2025 datasets permanently available through their portal. All the acquisition details will be included together with the data availability in TCIA, and subsequently in IDC, including Google and AWS Marketplaces, as part of their Public Datasets Programs.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The acquisition protocols are different across (and within each) contributing institution, as these represent scans of real routine clinical practice. Specific details (e.g., echo time, repetition time, original acquisition plane) of each scan of each patient will be published as supplementary material together with the challenge meta-analysis manuscript.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The provided data describe mpMRI scans, acquired with different clinical protocols and various scanners from:

Yale University School of Medicine

Northwestern University

University of Missouri

Duke University

Washington University

National Cancer University

University of California San Francisco

University of California San Diego

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Clinical staff involved in MRI acquisition for suspected and diagnosed brain tumor patients during standard clinical practice.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case describes multi-parametric MRI scans for a single patient at multiple timepoints. Pre-treatment and post-treatment scans are included in the datasets. The exact scans included for one case are i) unenhanced and ii)

contrast-enhanced T1-weighted, iii) T2-weighted and iv) T2 Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) MRI. Please note that all sequences included for each case of the provided dataset, represent the sequences with the best image quality available in the acquiring institution for this particular case. There was no inclusion/exclusion criterion applied that related to 3d acquisitions, or the exact type of pulse sequence (for example MPRAGE). We, instead, accepted all types of T1 acquisitions (with the exception of T1 FLAIR, as we did not want to mix the fluid suppressed values with non-flair scans) and then we applied the harmonized preprocessing protocol we have been using in BraTS, across the complete data. This preprocessing ensures all scans have 3D representations on a specific resolution (1mm³), and aligned to the same anatomical atlas.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Total amount of cases: 1778 (1046 pre-operative and 732 post-treatment)

Training data: 1296 cases

Validation data: 179 cases

Test data: 303 cases

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

For the purposes of the challenge, we are utilizing the dataset used in 2025, so all the images from the training and testing sets are annotated. In 2026, we will be performing a Quality Control on all the annotations within the dataset.

As mentioned in the initial novelty section, we will also be offering to the participants non-annotated cases to facilitate innovations in semi-supervised learning approaches.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Based on our preliminary data in glioblastoma and brain metastasis segmentation, the plateau for training segmentations of brain metastases is reached at approximately 150 cases using the nnU-Net algorithm (Merkaj et al, 2021). The training data provided is therefore sufficient to train the algorithm, but the dice for our best performing algorithms is still in the range of 0.6-0.7. Therefore, we plan to add additional refinement steps to the reference standard data and exclude lesions below 5 mm in size for the segmentation challenge. We will add an additional arm of challenge, which will only rank the accuracy of detection of individual lesions.

Merkaj S, Bousabarah K, Zeevi T, Lin M, Aboian MS. PACS-based glioma segmentation and grade prediction for clinical implementation, ASFNR-ASNR AI workshop, 2021

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We will provide an additional batch of 150 non-annotated cases from a Yale University longitudinal metastases dataset.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Reference standard is based on approval from 2 experienced neuroradiologists, following annotations from over 200 annotators (students, residents, postgraduate fellows). All annotations were reviewed by 3rd experienced neuroradiologist. In 2026 challenge, additional review will be performed by board certified neuroradiologist and artifacts within the dataset will be annotated with bounding box.

We will focus on datasets that have been shown to be problematic based on forum discussion – UCSD dataset. We will run one of the algorithms from the BraTS 2025 winners and one of the algorithms that was never trained on BraTS data (Rudie et al., 2021) on the training data and identify cases with dice <1 ; these cases will be re-annotated.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The data considered in the BraTS-METS 2026 challenge follows the paradigm of the BraTS 2021-2022 and BraTS-METS 2023-2025 challenge data. The annotation of these data followed a pre-defined clinically approved annotation protocol (defined by expert neuroradiologists), which was provided to all clinical annotators, describing in detail instructions on what the segmentations of each tumor sub-region should describe (see below for the summary of the specific instructions). The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations with preference placed on ITK-SNAP, and also follow either a complete manual annotation approach, or a hybrid approach where an automated approach is used to produce some initial annotations followed by their manual refinements. All segmentations are checked in the final step by one final annotator. In 2026 challenge, additional review will be performed by board certified neuroradiologist and artifacts will also be annotated under supervision of a trainee.

Summary of specific instructions:

the enhancing tumor (when present) delineates the hyperintense signal of the T1-Gd, after excluding the vessels. The longitudinal dataset will have only this label.

the necrotic core (when present) outlines regions appearing dark in both T1 and T1-Gd images (denoting necrosis/cysts), and darked regions in T1-Gd that appear brighter in T1.

iii) the tumor core, which is the union of the enhancing tumor and the necrotic core described in (i) and (ii) above.

iv) the farthest tumor extent including the edema (what is called the whole tumor), delineates the tissue represented by the abnormal T2-FLAIR envelope.

v) resection cavity delineates the resection of region within the brain in post-treatment cases.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

2023-2025: Each case was assigned to a pair of annotator-approver. Annotators spanned across various experience levels and clinical/academic ranks, while the approvers are experienced board-certified neuroradiologists (with >5 years of experience), listed in the "Organizers" section as "clinical evaluators and annotation approvers". The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations, and also follow either a complete manual annotation approach, or a hybrid approach where an automated approach is used to produce some initial annotations followed by their manual refinements. Once the annotators were satisfied with the produced annotations, they were passing these to two different approvers. Approver 1 is then responsible for signing off these annotations. Specifically, approver 1 would review the tumor annotations, in tandem with the corresponding MRI scans, and if the annotations were not of satisfactory quality they would be sent back to the annotators for further refinements. This iterative approach was followed for all cases, until their respective annotations reached satisfactory quality (according to approver 1). The segmentation mask from Approver 1 is passed blindly to Approver 2 for further refinement. The whole dataset is finally approved by "Final approver" to ensure consistency. The "final approver" makes the segmentation available and noted as final ground truth segmentation labels for these scans.

2026: Additional review step will be performed by board certified neuroradiologist under the observation of a trainee. Additional lesions will be scanned in previously annotated studies and artifacts will be labelled.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

There is only one annotation file per case in the training set. The pipeline for producing the ultimate ground truth annotations is described in c).

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All the multiparametric MRI cases within the dataset provided to the participants have undergone several pre-processing steps, based on Cancer Imaging Phenomics Toolkit (CaPTk) [1] and Federated Tumor Segmentation (FeTS) Tool [2]. The images were converted from Digital Imaging and Communication in Medicine (DICOM) files to Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NIFTI) file format. All protected information and metadata accompanying the DICOM images are removed. The cases from the UCSD and UCSF datasets comprise sequences co-registered in native space. The remaining cases are co-registered to the SRI24 multichannel atlas [3] of normal adult brain. All the cases are resampled to a uniform isotropic resolution 1mm³.

Skull-stripping and anonymization of the images was executed for all the cases within the dataset. The used approach was developed by Thakur et al. [4].

[1] S.Pati, et al. The cancer imaging phenomics toolkit (CaPTk): technical overview. International MICCAI

Brainlesion Workshop. Springer, Cham, 2019. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-46643-5_38

[2] S.Pati, et al, The federated tumor segmentation (FeTS) tool: an open-source solution to further solid tumor research, *Phys. Med. Biol.* 67(20), 204002, 2022. DOI: 10.1088/1361-6560/ac9449

[3] Rohlfing, T., Zahr, N. M., Sullivan, E. V., & Pfefferbaum, A. (2010). The SRI24 multichannel atlas of normal adult human brain structure. *Human brain mapping*, 31(5), 798–819. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hbm.20906>

[4] Thakur S, Doshi J, Pati S, et al. Brain extraction on MRI scans in presence of diffuse glioma: Multi-institutional performance evaluation of deep learning methods and robust modality-agnostic training. *NeuroImage*. 2020;220:117081. doi:10.1016/j.neuroimage.2020.117081

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

A comprehensive analysis of intra- and inter-rated variability will be submitted for publication in early 2026.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Subjectwise

Normalized Surface Distance (NSD), Subjectwise

Sensitivity, Lesionwise

Specificity, Lesionwise

Precision, Lesionwise

The regions evaluated using these metrics describe the whole tumor, the tumor core, and the enhancing tumor (when present). Note that the tumor core includes the part of the tumor that is typically resected (i.e., enhancing, non-enhancing, and necrotic tumor), and the whole tumor describes all tumor sub-regions (i.e., tumor core and edema/invasion).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

In terms of the assessed and evaluated tumor sub-regions:

i) the enhancing tumor describes the regions of active tumor with blood brain barrier breakdown and based on this, clinical practice characterizes the extent of resection based on removal of the contrast enhancing region.

ii) the tumor core (incl. the necrotic component) describes what is typically resected during a surgical procedure.

iii) the whole tumor as it defines the whole extent of the tumor, including the peritumoral edematous tissue and non-enhancing infiltrated area.

In terms of segmentation evaluation, we use the following subject-wise metrics:

i) the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), which is commonly used in the assessment of segmentation performance,

ii) Normalized Surface Distance (NSD), which introduces a tolerance parameter and is complementary to traditional metrics such as DSC

iii) Sensitivity and Specificity to determine whether an algorithm has the tendency to over- or undersegment.

iv) Precision to complement the metric of Sensitivity (also known as recall).

In terms of lesion detection evaluation, we use the following lesion-wise metrics:

i) F1 score – the harmonic mean of precision and recall

ii) AUC over multiple F1 scores, obtained at different detection threshold values

* We apply the detection evaluation for every single lesion within one MRI study. For the detection arm of the challenge we define a lesion as a collective term including the Enhancing Tumor, the Non-enhancing Tumor Core, and the Resection cavity.

* We will apply the segmentation evaluation metrics only for lesions larger than 27 mm^3 (The images in the dataset are co-registered to 1mm slice thickness)

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Ranking of methods will be based on the aggregate of rankings of Dice and NSD for segmentation and Sensitivity/Specificity for detection. Specifically, we will follow the DELPHI-based recommendations for image analysis validation [1,2], incorporating i) algorithmic ranking, and ii) statistical significance testing. Building upon the approach in BraTS 2017-2025, the performance of the tasks will be evaluated based on the relative

performance (as an aggregate metric of the ones described above) of each team's model in classifying different tumor tissue types. For this analysis we will divide the test data into multiple non-overlapping subsets, ensuring balanced class representation. The assessment will involve a detailed analysis of each model's performance for various tumor tissues. We then compute an average rank for each of the subsets across both metrics, and aggregated these average rankings to produce a conclusive overall ranking.

[1] Reinke et al. Understanding metric-related pitfalls in image analysis validation. *Nat Methods*. 2024 Feb;21(2):182-194.

[2] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. *Nat Methods*. 2024 Feb;21(2):195-212.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, this metric will be set to its worst possible value (e.g., 0 for Dice)

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For ranking of multidimensional outcomes (or metrics), for each team, we will compute the summation of their ranks across the average of the metrics described above as a univariate overall summary measure. This measure will decide the overall ranking for each specific team. To visualize the results in an intuitive fashion, we propose to visualize the outcome via an augmented version of radar plot (Duan et al, 2020).

Duan R, Tong J, Lin L, Levine LD, Sammel MD, Stoddard J, Li T, Schmid CH, Chu H, Chen Y. PALM: Patient-centered Treatment Ranking via Large-scale Multivariate Network Meta-analysis. *medRxiv*. 2020 Jan 1

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will leverage the same statistical framework we have been applying to BraTS over the last years, which provides a fair, transparent, and robust evaluation framework building upon two stages: (i) a ranking score generated for each evaluated method, based on case-wise cumulative rankings aggregated across the pre-specified metrics reported above and across unseen hold-out cases, and (ii) a rigorous statistical significance assessment, based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Compared to a simplistic ordinal ranking, this two-staged methodology provides a more holistic assessment of model performance, identifying if performance differences between any two models are statistically significant and systematic, or the result of chance on a particular test set.

The article describing in detail the exact method has been accepted and will be released as part of the MICCAI BraTS 2025 Springer LNCS proceedings.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD and IQR across test cases – visualized as violin plots in our meta-analysis article and presented at the time of the challenge. Furthermore, we report the mean, standard errors and outliers.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

One-sided test assessment – the methodological details of the test for significance span over 2 pages of the accepted article. Springer informed us that this article should be released within March 2026.

To maintain statistical rigor, a correction for multiple comparisons, such as the Bonferroni correction or controlling the False Discovery Rate, will be applied to the p-values before interpretation.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

N/A, as if an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, we set the scores to the worst possible rank for this case.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

The software that we will use is released as an open-source tool through GitHub (<https://github.com/IUCompPath/PermRanker>) and we anticipate the release of its accompanying article to be available in March 2026.

We will provide pointers to the article and the software in the challenge website.

We would be happy to update the design document once the article is available.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

TASK 2: BraTS-PEDS: Segmentation of pediatric brain tumor sub-regions in pre- and post-treatment MRI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Brain tumors are among the deadliest types of cancer, and the BraTS Challenge has a successful history of creating benchmark datasets and evaluation frameworks for segmentation and analysis of aggressive primary brain tumors. Although rare, pediatric brain and central nervous system tumors are the leading cause of cancer-related mortality in children and present distinct biological, clinical, and imaging characteristics compared to adult tumors. Pediatric diffuse midline gliomas (DMGs), for example, are high-grade tumors with poor prognosis, typically arising in the pons during early childhood, and often lack the classic imaging features observed in adult GBM, such as well-defined contrast enhancement and necrosis. These differences underscore the need for pediatric-specific imaging datasets and AI methods tailored to this population.

Building on the inclusion of pediatric DMGs in the BraTS 2022 test set and the success of the multi-institutional BraTS-PEDs 2023-2025 challenges, the BraTS-PEDs initiative continues to expand in scope and scale. For the BraTS-PEDs 2026 challenge, we will include both treatment-naïve and post-treatment pediatric brain tumor data. The treatment-naïve cohort comprises 457 pediatric subjects that have been publicly released through The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA). In addition, the 2026 challenge will introduce a longitudinal post-treatment cohort consisting of 35 patients with at least three MRI timepoints per subject (105 total post-treatment cases), enabling the evaluation of segmentation robustness in the setting of therapy-related changes.

The dataset is collected through multiple international consortia and institutions, including the Children's Brain Tumor Network (CBTN) and the DIPG/DMG Registry, and includes multiparametric MRI with expert-validated tumor subregion annotations. Participants will develop, containerize, and submit their algorithms via the Synapse platform, where models will be evaluated on unseen validation and testing cohorts under a standardized, reproducible framework. By incorporating both cross-sectional treatment-naïve imaging and longitudinal post-treatment data, BraTS-PEDs 2026 aims to advance robust, clinically relevant pediatric brain tumor segmentation methods and to better reflect real-world clinical scenarios encountered in pediatric neuro-oncology.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Segmentation, Detection, Challenge, Brain Tumor, Pediatric, Rare Disease, Diffuse Midline Glioma, CBTN, MICCAI

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Marius George Linguraru, D.Phil., M.A., M.Sc. - [Lead Organizer]

Children's National Hospital / George Washington University

Anahita Fathi Kazerooni, PhD, MSc - [Lead Organizer]

The Children's Hospital of Philadelphia / University of Pennsylvania

Additional members of the Organizing Team:

Deep Gandhi

The Children's Hospital of Philadelphia

Zhifan Jiang, Ph.D.

Children's National Hospital

Xinyang Liu, Ph.D.

Children's National Hospital

Spyridon Bakas, PhD

Department of Pathology & Laboratory Medicine, Indiana University, IN, USA

Mehdi Astaraki, PhD,

Karolinska Institute

Keyvan Farahani, PhD.

National Institutes of Health

Verena Chung,

Sage Bionetworks

Clinical Team:

Arastoo Vossough, MD

Children's Hospital of Philadelphia

Ali Nabavizadeh, MD

University of Pennsylvania

Jeffrey B Ware, MD

University of Pennsylvania

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Marius George Linguraru, D.Phil., M.A., M.Sc.
 Children's National Hospital / George Washington University
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Anahita Fathi Kazerooni, PhD, MSc
 The Children's Hospital of Philadelphia / University of Pennsylvania
 anahita.kazerooni@penncmedicine.upenn.edu

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Clinicians are integral members of the organizing team and play a key role in the clinical design, annotation, and evaluation of the challenge. Board-certified pediatric neuroradiologists are involved in defining clinically meaningful tumor subregions, developing and reviewing annotation protocols, supervising and approving reference standard segmentations, and advising on evaluation metrics to ensure clinical relevance. Clinicians also contribute to the interpretation of challenge results and help align the benchmarking framework with real-world pediatric neuro-oncology workflows and response assessment needs.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline, and continuous evaluation after the conference deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Synapse.org

Following our successful collaboration with the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks) since the RSNA-ASNR-MICCAI BraTS 2021 challenge, we have coordinated with them and following the support from NCI (represented by Dr Keyvan Farahani in the organizing committee - Chair of the NCI AI Challenges Working Group) Synapse will be used as the platform to drive the evaluation of this cluster of challenges.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS 2026 challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in a number of ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long-time co-organizer of BraTS challenges

and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC). All aforementioned NCI platforms are implemented on the Google Cloud Platform. This collaboration with Synapse, enabled by NCI/NIH support through ITCR grant (Synapse, PI) and other NCI resources represents a major advancement in the challenge design and leveraging of public resources.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026> - (Website will be publicly visible after the challenge approval)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

We are seeking the development of automated algorithms.

Participants must submit a fully automated container that no user interaction is required for successful execution.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples), as long as it does not involve resources unavailable to other participants. Example of such resources are: proprietary software, clinical expertise to create additional reference standard annotations.

Our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods. Thus, if participants have a solution that includes any resources unavailable to other participants, they are allowed to submit it, but if they do so, they **MUST** also submit a solution that does not include these resources and discuss the potential difference in their results between the two solutions.

We urge participants to coordinate with the organizers if there is any clarification required.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

All participants are allowed to use publicly available pre-trained models (e.g., foundation models), as well as additional data from datasets publicly available at the time of the challenge launch.

Since our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods, participating teams are allowed to even use data from their own institutions (unavailable to other participants) for further complementing the data, but if they do so, they MUST also discuss the potential difference in their results before and after using these "private" data.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but organizers and their immediate groups cannot be 1) eligible for awards, 2) announced as the winners of the challenge, or 3) included in the announced formal rankings. They will however be evaluated and if they are within the top-ranked ones they will be honorarily mentioned to contribute back to the community. Since organizing institutions are large, other employees from other labs/departments may participate and should be eligible for the awards and to be listed in the official leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge organizers are in communication with industrial partners and MICCAI SIGs, to sponsor monetary awards for the top 3 teams. Formal confirmation can only be provided after the acceptance of the challenge. Note that the organizers have been securing monetary awards during each of BraTS 2018-2025. NIH will also provide Certificates of Merit to the top 3 performing teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly at the conference and the participants will be invited to present their method during an oral presentation.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

We intend to coordinate 2 specific publication plans for BraTS 2026.

Plan 1:

Coordination of the BraTS proceedings as part of the MICCAI Satellite Event proceedings, allowing the BraTS participants to publish their methods in the associated MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings. We have already been publishing BraTS Springer proceedings since 2015. This year we will have the BraTS proceedings as part of the main MICCAI Satellite Event Springer LNCS proceedings.

Plan 2:

We coordinate a post-conference meta-analysis journal manuscript to summarize the results, findings, and insights of the 2026 challenge.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The participants are required to send the output of their methods to the evaluation platform for the scoring to occur during the training and the validation phases. At the end of the validation phase the participants are asked to identify the method they would like to evaluate in the final testing/ranking phase.

The organizers will then confirm receiving the containerized method and will evaluate it in the hidden testing data. The participants will be provided guidelines on the form of the container as we have done in previous years. This will enable confirmation of reproducibility.

During the training and validation phases, the participants will have the chance to test the functionality of their submission through both the implementation of the evaluation metrics (provided at the challenge website), as well as via the online evaluation platform (Synapse).

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We intend to publicly release the training and the validation sets, as soon as the challenge is approved but not later than April 2026, allowing participants to train and tune their methods. The validation data ground truth will not be provided to the participants, but multiple submissions to the online evaluation platform will be allowed for the validation phase. However, only 2 submissions will be allowed in the final testing/ranking data/phase to avoid potential tuning of the submitted approach to the testing data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration dates: From website opening until submission deadline of short papers reporting method and preliminary results (see below).

16 March 2026 (or earlier): Registration opens – Release of Training and Validation data
Participants will be able to register for the challenge in synapse.org, from the date of its potential acceptance (either Feb 9, or Mar 16, 2026) until the short paper submission deadline (July 31, 2026).
Availability of training data (with ground truth labels) and validation data (without ground truth labels).

31 July 2026: Submission deadline for Paper and Containerized method
Paper should include motivation, literature, method description, and results on training and validation data.
The containerized method will be evaluated on the hidden testing data by the organizers, only for participants with submitted short papers. Ranking of all participating methods, following statistical significance assessment based on multiple permutation testing.

7 August 2026: Initial invitations are sent
Inviting participants with a valid submitted paper and an evaluated container to present at the conference (type of presentation will be determined within the next 2 weeks)

14 August 2026: Paper reviews are available

19 August 2026: Release of summary testing results to each participant.
Participants will receive summary testing data results, in order to report those in their papers.

21 August 2026: Camera-ready paper and Copyright form submission deadline

24 August 2026: Contacting top-performing methods for preparing slides for oral presentation.

1 September 2026: Organizers to send all proceedings material to the MICCAI 2026 Satellite Event committee for inclusion in the MICCAI LNCS Springer Proceedings.

4-8 October 2026: Challenge at MICCAI
Announcement of final top 3 ranked teams

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Ethics approval is not required for the treatment-naïve data, as these cases have already been publicly released through The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.7937/dx5c-tj86>) in fully de-identified form.

The post-treatment longitudinal data are sourced from the Children's Brain Tumor Network (CBTN; <https://cbtn.org>), a biorepository that provides access to de-identified clinical and imaging data under controlled access. All contributing institutions to CBTN have obtained institutional review board (IRB) approval for data collection, and informed consent was obtained in accordance with CBTN policies. Data are shared only after

approval of a formal data access request through the CBTN portal.

For the BraTS-PEDs 2026 challenge, we will submit the required requests to CBTN for permission to publicly release a subset of fully anonymized, de-identified, and expert-annotated post-treatment imaging data for research and benchmarking purposes, in compliance with all applicable ethical and regulatory requirements.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC-BY, but for any of the non-TCIA contributors that object to this license, the specific subset of the BraTS data will be released under a CC-BY-NC license.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The implementation and references to the pre-processing tools, exact evaluation metrics, and the ranking code used during the whole challenge's lifecycle will be made available through the challenge's website (<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants are required to submit their containerized algorithm, during or after the validation phase. Specific instructions for the containerization will be provided after the challenge approval. These instructions will be very similar to what we were requesting participants to provide during the BraTS 2021-2025 challenges.

All challenge participants will be required to accept an agreement through the [synapse.org](https://www.synapse.org) website that participation in the testing phase of the challenge, will automatically mean that we can make their containerized method publicly available through our challenge webpage and a collective toolkit we are putting together.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in several ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long time co-organizer of BraTS challenges and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of

an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC) on the Google Cloud Platform

The organizers are in coordination with industrial collaborators to offer dissemination of top-ranked containerized methods for research use only, through their commercial platforms, subject to participating teams accepting this opportunity.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only challenge organizers (the challenge team and SAGE Bionetworks (synapse.org)) will have access to the validation and test case reference standard annotations.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research,CAD,Decision support,Treatment planning,Diagnosis,Assistance,Surgery,Intervention planning,Education,Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Detection

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Pediatric glioma patients

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Retrospective multi-institutional cohort of patients, diagnosed with pediatric brain tumors, clinically scanned with mpMRI acquisition protocol including i) pre-contrast and ii) contrast-enhanced T1-weighted, iii) T2-weighted and iv) T2-weighted Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) MRI.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Multi-parametric MRI scans of the brain, including T1-weighted, T2-weighted, FLAIR T2, and contrast-enhanced T1-weighted images.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information pertains directly to the image data (i.e., Tumor sub-region labels and volumes)

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

N/A

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain mpMRI scans in pediatric brain tumor patients before and after initiation of treatment.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with brain tumors, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Sensitivity, Specificity, Dice, Normalized Surface Distance

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The pediatric brain tumor images collected have been acquired on multiple scanners, including but not limited to 1.5T and 3T Siemens and GE scanners.

Acquisition details for a part of our data (treatment-naïve data) have been provided in our TCIA collection.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The acquisition protocols are different across (and within each) contributing institution, as these represent scans of real routine clinical practice. Specific details (e.g., echo time, repetition time, original acquisition plane) of each scan of each patient will be published as supplementary material together with the challenge meta-analysis manuscript.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The provided data describe mpMRI scans, acquired with different clinical protocols and various scanners from:

- Children's National Hospital (CBTN site)
- Children's Hospital of Philadelphia (CBTN site),
- Other CBTN sites
- Boston Children's Hospital
- Yale University
- Duke University
- Other sites in DIPG/DMG registry
- University of Michigan

Note that the treatment-naïve data from these institutions are provided through The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA; <http://www.cancerimagingarchive.net/>).

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Clinical staff involved in MRI acquisition for suspected and diagnosed brain tumor patients during standard clinical practice.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case describes multi-parametric MRI scans for a single patient at a single timepoint. The exact scans included for one case are i) unenhanced and ii) contrast-enhanced T1-weighted, iii) T2-weighted and iv) T2 Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) MRI.

Please note that all sequences included for each case of the provided dataset, represent the sequences with the best image quality available in the acquiring institution for this particular case. There was no inclusion/exclusion criterion applied that related to 3D acquisitions, or the exact type of pulse sequence (for example MPRAGE). We, instead, accepted all types of T1 acquisitions (with the exception of T1 FLAIR, as we did not want to mix the fluid suppressed values with non-flair scans) and then we applied the harmonized preprocessing protocol we have been using in BraTS, across the complete data. This preprocessing ensures all scans have 3D representations on a specific resolution (1mm³), and aligned to the same anatomical atlas.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The challenge dataset comprises both treatment-naïve and post-treatment pediatric brain tumor imaging data.

Treatment-naïve cohort (TCIA):

We have publicly released treatment-naïve data for 457 pediatric patients with high-grade gliomas through TCIA, divided as follows (one case per subject):

Training: 257 cases with expert-validated tumor segmentation masks

Validation: 91 cases without labels (used for leaderboard evaluation)

Testing: 109 cases forming a hidden cohort for final performance assessment

Post-treatment longitudinal cohort:

In addition, the BraTS-PEDs 2026 challenge will include post-treatment longitudinal data from 35 subjects, each with a minimum of three MRI timepoints, yielding 105 additional cases. These data are distributed as:

24 subjects (72 timepoints)

4 subjects (12 timepoints)

7 subjects (21 timepoints)

Overall dataset composition:

Across treatment-naïve and post-treatment data, the challenge includes a total of 562 subjects and 562 + longitudinal timepoints accounted as cases, with the following splits:

Training: 281 subjects, 329 cases (timepoints)

Validation: 95 subjects, 103 cases (timepoints)

Testing: 116 subjects, 130 cases (timepoints)

This design enables benchmarking on both cross-sectional treatment-naïve imaging and longitudinal post-treatment scans, better reflecting real-world clinical scenarios in pediatric neuro-oncology.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

81.3% of the total data is already annotated, including 78.1% of Training, 88.3 of Validation, and 83.8% of Testing Data.

As mentioned in the initial novelty section, we will also be offering to the participants non-annotated cases to facilitate innovations in semi-supervised learning approaches.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Based on availability, and while keeping in mind good machine learning practices.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

We will provide post-treatment data which has been unseen and unpublished before:

Post-treatment longitudinal cohort:

In addition, the BraTS-PEDs 2026 challenge will include post-treatment longitudinal data from 35 subjects, each with a minimum of three MRI timepoints, yielding 105 additional cases. These data are distributed as:

24 subjects (72 timepoints)

4 subjects (12 timepoints)

7 subjects (21 timepoints)

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Reference approved by at least 2 experienced neuroradiologists, following annotations from 6-8 clinical neuroradiologists (volunteers from ASNR)

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The data considered in BraTS-PEDs 2026 challenge follows the paradigm of the BraTS-PEDs 2024 challenge data. The annotation of these data followed a pre-defined clinically-approved annotation protocol (defined by a consensus of experienced pediatric neuroradiologists from the Children's Hospital of Philadelphia, with the annotation method published in [9]). This was provided to all clinical annotators, describing in detail instructions on what the segmentations of each tumor sub-region should describe (see below for the summary of the specific instructions). The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations, and also follow either a complete manual annotation approach, or a hybrid approach where an automated approach is used to produce some initial annotations followed by their manual refinements.

Summary of specific instructions:

Enhancing Tumor: This subregion is described by areas with enhancement (brightness) on T1 post-contrast images as compared to T1 pre-contrast. In case of mild enhancement, checking the signal intensity of normal brain structure can be helpful.

Cystic Component: The appearance of the cystic region is hyperintense (very bright) on T2 and hypointense (dark) on T1CE. The cystic portion should be within the tumor (versus edema which is peritumoral). The brightness is comparable to CSF.

Non-enhancing Tumor: Any abnormal signal intensity within the tumoral region that cannot be defined as enhancing or cystic. For example, the abnormal signal intensity on T1, FLAIR and T2 that is not enhancing on T1CE should be considered as non-enhancing portion.

Edema: This sub-region is defined by the abnormal hyperintense signal (very bright) on FLAIR scans. Edema is finger-like spreading that preserves underlying brain structure and surrounds the tumor.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each case was assigned to a pair of annotator-approver. Annotators spanned across various experience levels and clinical/academic ranks, while the approvers were the 3 experienced board-certified neuroradiologists (with >7 years of experience), listed in the "Organizers" section as "clinical evaluators and annotation approvers". The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations, and also follow either a complete manual annotation approach, or a hybrid approach where an automated approach is used to produce some initial annotations followed by their manual refinements. Once the annotators were satisfied with the produced annotations, they were passing these to the corresponding approver. The approver is then responsible for signing off these annotations. Specifically, the approver would review the tumor annotations, in tandem with the corresponding MRI scans, and if the annotations were not of satisfactory quality they would be sent back to the annotators for further refinements. This iterative approach was followed for all cases, until their respective annotations reached satisfactory quality (according to the approver) for being publicly available and noted as final ground truth segmentation labels for these scans.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No Aggregation.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The image preprocessing pipeline applied to all the data considered in the BraTS-PEDs 2025 challenge is identical with the one evaluated and followed by the BraTS 2017-2024 challenges, with the difference in applying pediatric-specific tumor subregion segmentation and automated defacing tools. Specifically, following the conversion of the raw scans from their original DICOM file format to NIfTI file format, we first perform a re-orientation of all input scans (T1, T1- Gd, T2, T2-FLAIR) to the LPS/RAI orientation, and then register all of them to the same anatomical atlas (i.e., SRI-24) and interpolating to the same resolution as this atlas (1 mm3).

After completion of the registration process, we will perform automated defacing based on an in-house pediatric-specific deep-learning tool, to remove some face features that may risk re-identification of the subjects. We will then manually review all scans for confirming the correct defacing, where the complete brain region is included, and all non-brain tissue is excluded.

This whole preprocessing pipeline, and its source code are available through the CaPTk (<https://github.com/CBICA/CaPTk>) and FeTS (<https://fets-ai.github.io/Front-End/>) platforms. Pediatric-specific automated defacing and tumor subregion segmentation methods will be available on <https://github.com/d3b-center/peds-brain-auto-seg-public> and <https://github.com/d3b-center/peds-auto-defacing-public>.

C.Davatzikos, et al., "Cancer imaging phenomics toolkit: quantitative imaging analytics for precision diagnostics and predictive modeling of clinical outcome." *Journal of medical imaging*, 5.1:011018 (2018) DOI:

10.1117/1.jmi.5.1.011018

S.Pati, et al., "The cancer imaging phenomics toolkit (CaPTk): technical overview." International MICCAI Brainlesion Workshop. Springer, Cham (2019) DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-46643-5_38

S.Pati, et al, "The federated tumor segmentation (FeTS) tool: an open-source solution to further solid tumor research", Phys. Med. Biol. 67(20), 204002, 2022. DOI: 10.1088/1361-6560/ac9449

Fathi Kazerooni A, et al. "Automated tumor segmentation and brain tissue extraction from multiparametric MRI of pediatric brain tumors: A multi-institutional study". Neuro-Oncology Advances. 2023 Jan 1;5(1):vdad027.

Vossough A, ..., Fathi Kazerooni A, "Training and Comparison of nnU-Net and DeepMedic Methods for Autosegmentation of Pediatric Brain Tumors". Under Review (American Journal of Neuroradiology)

Liu X, ..., Linguraru MG. "From adult to pediatric: deep learning-based automatic segmentation of rare pediatric brain tumors". In Medical Imaging 2023: Computer-Aided Diagnosis 2023 Apr 7 (Vol. 12465, pp. 15-19). SPIE.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Study and evaluation of the effect of this error is addressed by the uncertainty task of BraTS 2019-2020 (i.e., to quantify the uncertainty in the tumor segmentations) and is outside the scope of the BraTS 2026 Glioma challenge.

R.Mehta, et al, QU-BraTS: MICCAI BraTS 2020 Challenge on Quantifying Uncertainty in Brain Tumor Segmentation-Analysis of Ranking Scores and Benchmarking Results, Journal of Machine Learning for Biomedical Imaging, 1, 26, 2022

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Subjectwise

Normalized Surface Distance (NSD), Subjectwise

Sensitivity, Lesionwise

Specificity, Lesionwise

The regions evaluated using these metrics describe the enhancing tumor (ET), the cystic component (CC), the non-enhancing tumor (NET), the tumor core (TC), the edema (ED), and the whole tumor (WT). Note that the tumor core includes the part of the tumor that is typically resected (i.e., including ET, CC, and NET), and the whole tumor describes all tumor sub-regions (i.e., tumor core and edema/invasion).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

In terms of the assessed and evaluated tumor sub-regions:

- 1) the enhancing tumor describes the regions of active tumor and based on this, clinical practice characterizes the extent of resection.
- 2) the cystic component appears with hyperintense signal (very bright) on T2 and hypointense signal (dark) on T1CE.
- 3) the non-enhancing tumor describes any other abnormal signal intensity within the tumorous region that cannot be defined as enhancing or cystic.
- 4) the tumor core (incl. the necrotic component) describes what is typically resected during a surgical procedure.
- 5) the peritumoral edema defined by the abnormal hyperintense signal (very bright) on FLAIR scans.
- 6) the whole tumor as it defines the whole extent of the tumor, including the peritumoral edematous tissue and highly infiltrated area.

In terms of segmentation evaluation, we use the following subject-wise metrics:

- i) the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), which is commonly used in the assessment of segmentation performance,
- ii) Normalized Surface Distance (NSD), which introduces a tolerance parameter and is complementary to traditional metrics such as DSC
- iii) Sensitivity and Specificity to determine whether an algorithm has the tendency to over- or undersegment.
- iv) Precision to complement the metric of Sensitivity (also known as recall).

In terms of lesion detection evaluation, we use the following lesion-wise metrics:

i) F1 score – the harmonic mean of precision and recall

ii) AUC over multiple F1 scores, obtained at different detection threshold values

* We apply the detection evaluation for every single lesion within one MRI study. For the detection arm of the challenge we define a lesion as a collective term including the Enhancing Tumor, the Non-enhancing Tumor Core, and the Resection cavity.

* We will apply the segmentation evaluation metrics only for lesions larger than 27 mm^3 (The images in the dataset are co-registered to 1mm slice thickness)

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Ranking of methods will be based on the aggregate of rankings of Dice and NSD for segmentation and Sensitivity/Specificity for detection. Specifically, we will follow the DELPHI-based recommendations for image analysis validation [1,2], incorporating i) algorithmic ranking, and ii) statistical significance testing. Building upon the approach in BraTS 2017-2025, the performance of the tasks will be evaluated based on the relative performance (as an aggregate metric of the ones described above) of each team's model in classifying different tumor tissue types. For this analysis we will divide the test data into multiple non-overlapping subsets, ensuring balanced class representation. The assessment will involve a detailed analysis of each model's performance for various tumor tissues. We then compute an average rank for each of the subsets across both metrics, and aggregated these average rankings to produce a conclusive overall ranking.

[1] Reinke et al. Understanding metric-related pitfalls in image analysis validation. Nat Methods. 2024 Feb;21(2):182-194.

[2] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nat Methods. 2024 Feb;21(2):195-212.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, this metric will be set to its worst possible value (e.g., 0 for Dice)

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For ranking of multidimensional outcomes (or metrics), for each team, we will compute the summation of their ranks across the average of the metrics described above as a univariate overall summary measure. This measure will decide the overall ranking for each specific team. To visualize the results in an intuitive fashion, we propose to visualize the outcome via an augmented version of radar plot (Duan et al, 2020).

Duan R, Tong J, Lin L, Levine LD, Sammel MD, Stoddard J, Li T, Schmid CH, Chu H, Chen Y. PALM: Patient-centered Treatment Ranking via Large-scale Multivariate Network Meta-analysis. medRxiv. 2020 Jan 1

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will leverage the same statistical framework we have been applying to BraTS over the last years, which provides a fair, transparent, and robust evaluation framework building upon two stages: (i) a ranking score generated for each evaluated method, based on case-wise cumulative rankings aggregated across the pre-specified metrics reported above and across unseen hold-out cases, and (ii) a rigorous statistical significance assessment, based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Compared to a simplistic ordinal ranking, this two-staged methodology provides a more holistic assessment of model performance, identifying if performance differences between any two models are statistically significant and systematic, or the result of chance on a particular test set.

The article describing in detail the exact method has been accepted and will be released as part of the MICCAI BraTS 2025 Springer LNCS proceedings.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD and IQR across test cases – visualized as violin plots in our meta-analysis article and presented at the time of the challenge. Furthermore, we report the mean, standard errors and outliers.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

One-sided test assessment – the methodological details of the test for significance span over 2 pages of the accepted article. Springer informed us that this article should be released within March 2026.

To maintain statistical rigor, a correction for multiple comparisons, such as the Bonferroni correction or controlling the False Discovery Rate, will be applied to the p-values before interpretation.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

N/A, as if an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, we set the scores to the worst possible rank for this case.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

The software that we will use is released as an open-source tool through GitHub (<https://github.com/IUCompPath/PermRanker>) and we anticipate the release of its accompanying article to be

available in March 2026.

We will provide pointers to the article and the software in the challenge website.

We would be happy to update the design document once the article is available.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

TASK 3: BraTS-GoAT: Segmentation generalizability of brain tumor sub-regions across tumors in pre-operative MRI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The International Brain Tumor Segmentation (BraTS) challenge has been focusing, since its inception in 2012, on generating a benchmark environment and dataset for delineating adult brain gliomas. In 2023, we expanded the dataset to include 1) the original adult gliomas population, as well as 2) the under-served sub-Saharan African brain gliomas patient population, 3) brain/intracranial meningiomas, 4) brain metastasis, and 5) pediatric brain tumor patients. This allowed us to organize different challenges, each focusing on specific clinical tasks. In this challenge, the BraTS Generalizability Across Tumors (BraTS-GoAT) Challenge, we will focus on assessing the algorithmic generalizability beyond each patient population and focus across all of them. The hypothesis is that a method capable of performing well on multiple segmentation tasks will generalize well on unseen tasks. Specifically, we aim to challenge participants to create a segmentation algorithm capable of adapting and generalizing to different scenarios with little prior information and/or data on the target class(es). We aim to simulate the clinical scenario where we develop a segmentation tool agnostic to future clinical applications (i.e., a tool trained on a specific disease(s) that will be applied to new ones).

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Generalizability, Segmentation, Brain, Tumors, RANO, MICCAI.

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Ujjwal Baid, PhD - [Lead Organizer]

Emory University

Gian Marco Conte, MD PhD

Mayo Clinic

Spyridon Bakas, PhD,

Indiana University School of Medicine

Dominic LaBella

Duke University

Mehdi Astaraki, PhD,
Karolinska Institute

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Children's Hospital of Philadelphia, Philadelphia, PA, USA

Nikolay Y. Yordanov, MD [Trainee Lead]
Multiprofile Hospital for Active Treatment in Neurology and Psychiatry, Sofia, Bulgaria

Maria Correia de Verdier, MD PhD,
Uppsala University

Florian Kofler, PhD,
Hertie Institute for AI in Brain Health

Keyvan Farahani, PhD,
National Institutes of Health

Evan Calabrese
Duke University

Nazanin Maleki, MD,
Children's Hospital of Philadelphia

Ahmed Moawad, MD,
Mercy Catholic Medical Center

Raisa Amiruddin, MBBS,
Children's Hospital of Philadelphia

Jeffrey Rudie MD PhD,
University of California, San Diego

Yury Velichko PhD,
Northwestern University

Marina Ivory,
King's College London

Matthew W. Pease, MD
Indiana University School of Medicine

Verena Chung,

Sage Bionetworks

Marius Linguraru

Children's National Hospital / George Washington University

Anahita Fathi Kazerooni

The Children's Hospital of Philadelphia / University of Pennsylvania

Udunna Anazodo

McGill University

Maruf Adewole

University of Pennsylvania

Juan Eugenio Iglesias

Harvard Medical School

Bjoern Menze

University of Zurich

Benedikt Wiestler

Technical University of Munich

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Ujjwal Baid, PhD

Emory University

ujjwal.raghunandan.baid@emory.edu

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Roles included 1) ensuring and increasing clinical relevance, 2) generation of annotations, 3) definition of annotation protocol, 4) review of reference standard, 5) interpretation of results.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Synapse.org

Following our successful collaboration with the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks) since the RSNA-ASNR-MICCAI BraTS 2021 challenge, we have coordinated with them and following the support from NCI (represented by Dr Keyvan Farahani in the organizing committee - Chair of the NCI AI Challenges Working Group) Synapse will be used as the platform to drive the evaluation of this cluster of challenges.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS 2026 challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in a number of ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long-time co-organizer of BraTS challenges and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC). All aforementioned NCI platforms are implemented on the Google Cloud Platform. This collaboration with Synapse, enabled by NCI/NIH support through ITCR grant (Synapse, PI) and other NCI resources represents a major advancement in the challenge design and leveraging of public resources.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026> - (Website will be publicly visible after the challenge approval)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

We are seeking the development of automated algorithms.

Participants must submit a fully automated container that no user interaction is required for successful execution.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples), as long as it does not involve resources unavailable to other participants. Example of such resources are: proprietary software, clinical expertise to create additional reference standard annotations.

Our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods. Thus, if participants have a solution that includes any resources unavailable to other participants, they are allowed to submit it, but if they do so, they **MUST** also submit a solution that does not include these resources and discuss the potential difference in their results between the two solutions.

We urge participants to coordinate with the organizers if there is any clarification required.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

All participants are allowed to use publicly available pre-trained models (e.g., foundation models), as well as additional data from datasets publicly available at the time of the challenge launch.

Since our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods, participating teams are allowed to even use data from their own institutions (unavailable to other participants) for further complementing the data, but if they do so, they **MUST** also discuss the potential difference in their results before and after using these “private” data.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but organizers and their immediate groups cannot be 1) eligible for awards, 2) announced as the winners of the challenge, or 3) included in the announced formal rankings. They will however be evaluated and if they are within the top-ranked ones they will be honorarily mentioned to contribute back to the community. Since organizing institutions are large, other employees from other labs/departments may participate and should be eligible for the awards and to be listed in the official leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge organizers are in communication with industrial partners and MICCAI SIGs, to sponsor monetary awards for the top 3 teams. Formal confirmation can only be provided after the acceptance of the challenge. Note that the organizers have been securing monetary awards during each of BraTS 2018-2025. NIH will also provide Certificates of Merit to the top 3 performing teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly at the conference and the participants will be invited to present their method during an oral presentation.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

We intend to coordinate 2 specific publication plans for BraTS 2026.

Plan 1:

Coordination of the BraTS proceedings as part of the MICCAI Satellite Event proceedings, allowing the BraTS participants to publish their methods in the associated MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings. We have already been publishing BraTS Springer proceedings since 2015. This year we will have the BraTS proceedings as part of the main MICCAI Satellite Event Springer LNCS proceedings.

Plan 2:

We coordinate a post-conference meta-analysis journal manuscript to summarize the results, findings, and insights of the 2026 challenge.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The participants are required to send the output of their methods to the evaluation platform for the scoring to occur during the training and the validation phases. At the end of the validation phase the participants are asked to identify the method they would like to evaluate in the final testing/ranking phase.

The organizers will then confirm receiving the containerized method and will evaluate it in the hidden testing data. The participants will be provided guidelines on the form of the container as we have done in previous years. This will enable confirmation of reproducibility.

During the training and validation phases, the participants will have the chance to test the functionality of their submission through both the implementation of the evaluation metrics (provided at the challenge website), as well as via the online evaluation platform (Synapse).

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We intend to publicly release the training and the validation sets, as soon as the challenge is approved but not later than April 2026, allowing participants to train and tune their methods. The validation data ground truth will

not be provided to the participants, but multiple submissions to the online evaluation platform will be allowed for the validation phase. However, only 2 submissions will be allowed in the final testing/ranking data/phase to avoid potential tuning of the submitted approach to the testing data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration dates: From website opening until submission deadline of short papers reporting method and preliminary results (see below).

16 March 2026 (or earlier): Registration opens – Release of Training and Validation data

Participants will be able to register for the challenge in synapse.org, from the date of its potential acceptance (either Feb 9, or Mar 16, 2026) until the short paper submission deadline (July 31, 2026).

Availability of training data (with ground truth labels) and validation data (without ground truth labels).

31 July 2026: Submission deadline for Paper and Containerized method

Paper should include motivation, literature, method description, and results on training and validation data.

The containerized method will be evaluated on the hidden testing data by the organizers, only for participants with submitted short papers. Ranking of all participating methods, following statistical significance assessment based on multiple permutation testing.

7 August 2026: Initial invitations are sent

Inviting participants with a valid submitted paper and an evaluated container to present at the conference (type of presentation will be determined within the next 2 weeks)

14 August 2026: Paper reviews are available

19 August 2026: Release of summary testing results to each participant.

Participants will receive summary testing data results, in order to report those in their papers.

21 August 2026: Camera-ready paper and Copyright form submission deadline

24 August 2026: Contacting top-performing methods for preparing slides for oral presentation.

1 September 2026: Organizers to send all proceedings material to the MICCAI 2026 Satellite Event committee for inclusion in the MICCAI LNCS Springer Proceedings.

4-8 October 2026: Challenge at MICCAI

Announcement of final top 3 ranked teams

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The BraTS-GoAT challenge is using datasets from other BraTS challenges spanning across various tumor entities. Each data-contributor has acquired the necessary ethics approval.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC-BY, but for any of the non-TCIA contributors that object to this license, the specific subset of the BraTS data will be released under a CC-BY-NC license.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The implementation and references to the pre-processing tools, exact evaluation metrics, and the ranking code used during the whole challenge's lifecycle will be made available through the challenge's website (<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants are required to submit their containerized algorithm, during or after the validation phase. Specific instructions for the containerization will be provided after the challenge approval. These instructions will be very similar to what we were requesting participants to provide during the BraTS 2021-2025 challenges.

All challenge participants will be required to accept an agreement through the synapse.org website that participation in the testing phase of the challenge, will automatically mean that we can make their containerized method publicly available through our challenge webpage and a collective toolkit we are putting together.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in several ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long time co-organizer of BraTS challenges and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC) on the Google Cloud Platform

The organizers are in coordination with industrial collaborators to offer dissemination of top-ranked containerized methods for research use only, through their commercial platforms, subject to participating teams accepting this opportunity.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Only the organizing team will have access to the test data.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research,CAD,Decision support,Treatment planning,Diagnosis,Assistance,Surgery,Intervention planning,Education,Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation,Detection

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Adult and pediatric brain tumor patients

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Retrospective multi-institutional cohort of patients, diagnosed with pediatric brain tumors, clinically scanned with mpMRI acquisition protocol including i) pre-contrast and ii) contrast-enhanced T1-weighted, iii) T2-weighted and iv) T2-weighted Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) MRI.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Multi-parametric MRI scans of the brain, including T1-weighted, T2-weighted, FLAIR T2, and contrast-enhanced T1-weighted images.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information pertains directly to the image data (i.e., Tumor sub-region labels and volumes)

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

N/A

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain mpMRI scans in adult and pediatric patients with brain tumors before initiation of treatment.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with brain tumors, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Sensitivity, Specificity, Dice, Normalized Surface Distance

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The exact scanners and their technical specifications used for acquiring the data used in this challenge span across multiple institutions and acquisition protocols published across the BraTS glioma, pediatrics, sub-Saharan Africa, and meningioma related manuscripts, as well as in the TCIA data collections for each sequence separately.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The acquisition protocols are different across (and within each) contributing institution, as these represent scans of real routine clinical practice. Specific details (e.g., echo time, repetition time, original acquisition plane) of each scan of each patient will be published as supplementary material together with the challenge meta-analysis manuscript.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The provided data describe mpMRI scans, acquired with different clinical protocols and various scanners from the following contributing sites to the respective BraTS challenges:

Adult glioma segmentation task of BraTS 2021-2022:

University of Pennsylvania (PA, USA), University of Alabama at Birmingham (AL, USA), Heidelberg University (Germany), University of Bern (Switzerland), University of Debrecen (Hungary), Henry Ford Hospital (MI, USA), University of California (CA, USA), MD Anderson Cancer Center (TX, USA), Emory University (GA, USA), Mayo Clinic (MN, USA), Thomas Jefferson University (PA, USA), Duke University School of Medicine (NC, USA), Saint Joseph Hospital and Medical Center (AZ, USA), Case Western Reserve University (OH, USA), University of North Carolina (NC, USA), Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Neurologico C. Besta, (Italy), Ivy Glioblastoma Atlas Project, MD Anderson Cancer Center (TX, USA), Washington University in St. Louis (MO, USA), Tata Memorial Center (India), University of Pittsburg Medical Center (PA, USA), University of California San Francisco (CA, USA), Unity Health, University Hospital of Zurich.

sub-Saharan Africa brain tumor segmentation task:

Crestview Radiology, Lagos, Nigeria (1.5 T Siemens), Lagos University Teaching Hospital, Lagos Nigeria (1.5T Toshiba/Canon), Lagos State University Teaching Hospital, Lagos Nigeria (1.5T Philips), The National Hospital, Abuja, Nigeria (1.5 T Toshiba), Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital, Lagos, Nigeria (1.5 T Siemens), Lily Hospital, Benin (1.5T GE), Medhub Africa (multi-scanner)

Adult meningioma segmentation task from the BraTS 2023 Meningioma challenge:

Duke University, University of Pennsylvania, Missouri University, University of California San Francisco, Yale University, Thomas Jefferson University

Adult metastasis segmentation task:

Yale University School of Medicine, Northwestern University, University of Missouri, Duke University, Washington University, National Cancer University, University of California San Francisco, University of California San Diego

Pediatric brain tumor segmentation task:

Children's National Hospital, Children's Hospital of Philadelphia, Boston Children's Hospital, Yale University, Duke University, University of Michigan.

Note that the treatment-naïve data from these institutions are provided through The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA; <http://www.cancerimagingarchive.net/>).

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Clinical staff involved in MRI acquisition for suspected and diagnosed brain tumor patients during standard clinical practice.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case describes multi-parametric MRI scans for a single patient at the pre-treatment timepoint. The exact scans included for one case are i) unenhanced and ii) contrast-enhanced T1-weighted, iii) T2-weighted and iv) T2 Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) MRI. Please note that all sequences included for each case of the provided dataset, represent the sequences with the best image quality available in the acquiring institution for this particular case. There was no inclusion/exclusion criterion applied that related to 3d acquisitions, or the exact type of pulse sequence (for example MPRAGE). We, instead, accepted all types of T1 acquisitions (with the exception of T1 FLAIR, as we did not want to mix the fluid suppressed values with non-flair scans) and then we applied the harmonized preprocessing protocol we have been using in BraTS, across the complete data. This preprocessing ensures all scans have 3D representations on a specific resolution (1mm³), and aligned to the same anatomical atlas.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

>16,000 mpMRI scans from >4,000 subjects will be used in this challenge.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data that should be annotated are already annotated. No further annotation efforts are needed for this year's challenge.

As mentioned in the initial novelty section, we will also be offering to the participants non-annotated cases to facilitate innovations in semi-supervised learning approaches.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Based on availability, and while keeping in mind good machine learning practices.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

No new annotated data will be provided in this year's challenge.

The testing data has always remained unseen and not published.

New data used in this year's challenge describe non-annotated cases to enable innovation in semi-supervised approaches.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The tumor segmentations were derived from previous BraTS segmentation challenges, involving expert neuro-radiologists from the RSNA and ASNR societies.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The tumor image annotation follows the paradigm of the BraTS 2023 challenge data. The annotation of these data followed a pre-defined clinically-approved annotation protocol (defined by expert neuroradiologists), which was provided to all clinical annotators, describing in detail instructions on what the segmentations of each tumor subregion should describe (see below for the summary of the specific instructions). The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations, and also follow either a complete manual annotation approach, or a hybrid approach where an automated approach is used to produce some initial annotations followed by their manual refinements.

Summary of specific instructions:

the enhancing tumor (when present) delineates the hyperintense signal of the T1-Gd, after excluding the vessels. the necrotic core (when present) outlines regions appearing dark in both T1 and T1-Gd images (denoting necrosis/cysts), and darked regions in T1-Gd that appear brighter in T1. iii) the tumor core, which is the union of the enhancing tumor and the necrotic core described in (i) and (ii) above. iv) the farthest tumor extent including the edema (what is called the whole tumor), delineates the tissue represented by the abnormal T2-FLAIR envelope.

These segmentations serve as input for our algorithm (see above) and are then curated by trained experts to make sure they do not contain other pathologies. The medical domain experts were proposed with several sample regions and selected the best candidates in an iterative process. Some patients had to be excluded from the test sets as the domain experts could not find healthy brain due to comorbidities. For more details please refer to our challenge manuscript.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each case was assigned to a pair of annotator-approver. Annotators spanned across various experience levels and clinical/academic ranks, while the approvers were 2 experienced board-certified neuroradiologists (with >15

years of experience). The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations, and also follow either a complete manual annotation approach, or a hybrid approach where an automated approach is used to produce some initial annotations followed by their manual refinements. Once the annotators were satisfied with the produced annotations, they were passing these to the corresponding approver. The approver is then responsible for signing off these annotations. Specifically, the approver would review the tumor annotations, in tandem with the corresponding MRI scans, and if the annotations were not of satisfactory quality they would be sent back to the annotators for further refinements. This iterative approach was followed for all cases, until their respective annotations reached satisfactory quality (according to the approver) for being publicly available and noted as final reference standard segmentation labels for these scans.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No Aggregation.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The exact preprocessing pipeline applied to all the data considered in the BraTS 2026 challenge is identical with the one evaluated and followed by the BraTS 2017-2025 challenges. Specifically, following the conversion of the raw scans from their original DICOM file format to NIfTI file format, we first perform a re-orientation of all input scans (T1, T1- Gd, T2, T2-FLAIR) to the LPS/RAI orientation, and then register all of them to the same anatomical atlas (i.e., SRI-24) and interpolating to the same resolution as this atlas (1 mm³). The exact registration process comprises the following steps:

STEP 1: N4 Bias field correction (notably the application of N4 bias field correction is a temporary step. Taking into consideration we have previously shown that the use of non-parametric, non-uniform intensity normalization (i.e., N4) to correct for intensity non-uniformities caused by the inhomogeneity of the scanners magnetic field during image acquisition obliterates the MRI signal relating to the abnormal/tumor regions, we intentionally use N4 bias field correction in the preprocessing pipeline to facilitate a more optimal rigid registration across the difference MRI sequences. However, after obtaining the related information (i.e., transformation matrices), we discard the bias field corrected scans, and we apply this transformation matrix towards the final co-registered output images used in the challenge).

STEP 2: Rigid Registration of T1, T2, T2-FLAIR to the T1-Gd scan, and obtain the corresponding transformation matrix.

STEP 3: Rigid Registration of T1-Gd scan to the SRI-24 atlas, and obtain the corresponding transformation matrix.

STEP 4: Join the obtained transformation matrices and applying aggregated transformation to the LPS-oriented scans.

STEP 5: After completion of the registration process, we perform brain extraction to remove any apparent nonbrain tissue (e.g., neck fat, skull, eyeballs) based on a deep-learning approach we developed in house, focusing on scans with apparent brain tumors and exhaustively evaluated it in both private and public

multi-institutional data. We then manually assessed all scans for confirming the correct brain extraction (i.e., skull stripping), where the complete brain region is included, and all non-brain tissue is excluded.

This whole pipeline, and its source code are available through the CaPTk (<https://github.com/CBICA/CaPTk>) and FeTS (<https://fets-ai.github.io/Front-End/>) platforms.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Study and evaluation of the effect of this error is addressed by the uncertainty task of BraTS 2019-2020 (i.e., to quantify the uncertainty in the tumor segmentations) and is outside the scope of the BraTS 2025 Glioma challenge.

R.Mehta, et al, QU-BraTS: MICCAI BraTS 2020 Challenge on Quantifying Uncertainty in Brain Tumor Segmentation-Analysis of Ranking Scores and Benchmarking Results, Journal of Machine Learning for Biomedical Imaging, 1, 26, 2022

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Subjectwise

Normalized Surface Distance (NSD), Subjectwise

Sensitivity, Lesionwise

Specificity, Lesionwise

Precision, Lesionwise

The regions evaluated using these metrics describe the whole tumor, the tumor core, and the enhancing tumor (when present). Note that the tumor core includes the part of the tumor that is typically resected (i.e., enhancing, non-enhancing, and necrotic tumor), and the whole tumor describes all tumor sub-regions (i.e., tumor core and edema/invasion).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

In terms of the assessed and evaluated tumor sub-regions:

- i) the enhancing tumor describes the regions of active tumor with blood brain barrier breakdown and based on this, clinical practice characterizes the extent of resection based on removal of the contrast enhancing region.
- ii) the tumor core (incl. the necrotic component) describes what is typically resected during a surgical procedure.
- iii) the whole tumor as it defines the whole extent of the tumor, including the peritumoral edematous tissue and non-enhancing infiltrated area.

In terms of segmentation evaluation, we use the following subject-wise metrics:

- i) the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), which is commonly used in the assessment of segmentation performance,
- ii) Normalized Surface Distance (NSD), which introduces a tolerance parameter and is complementary to traditional metrics such as DSC
- iii) Sensitivity and Specificity to determine whether an algorithm has the tendency to over- or undersegment.
- iv) Precision to complement the metric of Sensitivity (also known as recall).

In terms of lesion detection evaluation, we use the following lesion-wise metrics:

- i) F1 score – the harmonic mean of precision and recall
- ii) AUC over multiple F1 scores, obtained at different detection threshold values

* We apply the detection evaluation for every single lesion within one MRI study. For the detection arm of the challenge we define a lesion as a collective term including the Enhancing Tumor, the Non-enhancing Tumor Core, and the Resection cavity.

* We will apply the segmentation evaluation metrics only for lesions larger than 27 mm³ (The images in the dataset are co-registered to 1mm slice thickness)

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Ranking of methods will be based on the aggregate of rankings of Dice and NSD for segmentation and Sensitivity/Specificity for detection. Specifically, we will follow the DELPHI-based recommendations for image analysis validation [1,2], incorporating i) algorithmic ranking, and ii) statistical significance testing. Building upon the approach in BraTS 2017-2025, the performance of the tasks will be evaluated based on the relative

performance (as an aggregate metric of the ones described above) of each team's model in classifying different tumor tissue types. For this analysis we will divide the test data into multiple non-overlapping subsets, ensuring balanced class representation. The assessment will involve a detailed analysis of each model's performance for various tumor tissues. We then compute an average rank for each of the subsets across both metrics, and aggregated these average rankings to produce a conclusive overall ranking.

[1] Reinke et al. Understanding metric-related pitfalls in image analysis validation. *Nat Methods*. 2024 Feb;21(2):182-194.

[2] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. *Nat Methods*. 2024 Feb;21(2):195-212.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, this metric will be set to its worst possible value (e.g., 0 for Dice)

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

For ranking of multidimensional outcomes (or metrics), for each team, we will compute the summation of their ranks across the average of the metrics described above as a univariate overall summary measure. This measure will decide the overall ranking for each specific team. To visualize the results in an intuitive fashion, we propose to visualize the outcome via an augmented version of radar plot (Duan et al, 2020).

Duan R, Tong J, Lin L, Levine LD, Sammel MD, Stoddard J, Li T, Schmid CH, Chu H, Chen Y. PALM: Patient-centered Treatment Ranking via Large-scale Multivariate Network Meta-analysis. *medRxiv*. 2020 Jan 1

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will leverage the same statistical framework we have been applying to BraTS over the last years, which provides a fair, transparent, and robust evaluation framework building upon two stages: (i) a ranking score generated for each evaluated method, based on case-wise cumulative rankings aggregated across the pre-specified metrics reported above and across unseen hold-out cases, and (ii) a rigorous statistical significance assessment, based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Compared to a simplistic ordinal ranking, this two-staged methodology provides a more holistic assessment of model performance, identifying if performance differences between any two models are statistically significant and systematic, or the result of chance on a particular test set.

The article describing in detail the exact method has been accepted and will be released as part of the MICCAI BraTS 2025 Springer LNCS proceedings.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD and IQR across test cases – visualized as violin plots in our meta-analysis article and presented at the time of the challenge. Furthermore, we report the mean, standard errors and outliers.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

One-sided test assessment – the methodological details of the test for significance span over 2 pages of the accepted article. Springer informed us that this article should be released within March 2026.

To maintain statistical rigor, a correction for multiple comparisons, such as the Bonferroni correction or controlling the False Discovery Rate, will be applied to the p-values before interpretation.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

N/A, as if an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, we set the scores to the worst possible rank for this case.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

The software that we will use is released as an open-source tool through GitHub (<https://github.com/IUCompPath/PermRanker>) and we anticipate the release of its accompanying article to be available in March 2026.

We will provide pointers to the article and the software in the challenge website.

We would be happy to update the design document once the article is available.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

TASK 4: BraTS-Inpainting: Image synthesis (Inpainting) of brain tumor MRI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

The challenge's task is to inpaint healthy tissue in partially broken MRI scans. Reasons for this are often technical: there may be a presence of locally isolated artifacts, incompleteness of the field of view, or corrupted/missing 2D slices. For such cases, one may want to inpaint missing information locally instead of inferring the corrupted image volume completely. Therefore, our call is for algorithms capable of inpainting corrupted image intensities within a given inpainting mask. Like in the global image synthesis challenge, this will enable the application of the downstream image processing routines. For example, brain parcellation algorithms strictly require the input of normal-appearing images used in neuro-imaging studies and in brain tumor treatment planning. From a technical standpoint, these algorithms need to overcome a multitude of challenges that also apply to the global synthesis challenge:

First, the image resolutions of the individual sequences might differ; for example, FLAIR images tend to be acquired using 2D sequences, leading to anisotropic resolution, matching the resolution of other 3D imaging sequences only poorly. Second, motion artifacts may be presented in some of the sequences. At the same time, MRI bias fields may differ in their local impact on the different image modalities, leading to spatially inconstant artifacts. Third, a general domain shift between the training and test sets due to different acquisition settings and types of scanners can be expected to be present in almost any large and multi-institutional dataset. All these effects must be considered when developing methods for synthesizing MRI locally and globally. Questions about how to deal with these challenges, for example, by choosing adequate metrics or invariance properties of the algorithms and network architecture, have yet to be answered. In previous BraTS challenges, we have set up publicly available datasets and algorithms for multi-modal brain glioma segmentation. In our challenge task for MRI synthesis, we will build on these efforts, and the previously generated data sets, to further the development of much-needed computational tools for data integration and homogenization. It will enable better integration with other downstream routines used for quantitative neuro-image analysis (that only work well for brain images without perturbations from artifacts or lesions). The resulting MRI synthesis is essential to develop effective, generalizable, reproducible methods for analyzing high-resolution MRI of brain tumors. It will include data from multiple sites well established in previous BraTS challenges, adding new inference tasks beyond image segmentation. The resulting algorithms will have the potential to benefit automated brain (tumor) image processing and improve clinical risk stratification tools for early interventions, treatments, and care management decisions across hospitals and research institutions worldwide.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Inpainting, Synthesis, Challenge, Infill, Segmentation, Brain Tumor, MICCAI

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Florian Kofler

Hertie AI institute for brain health, University of Tübingen

Juan Eugenio Iglesias

Harvard Medical School

Bjoern Menze

University of Zurich

Marie Piraud

Helmholtz Research Center

Benedikt Wiestler

Technical University of Munich

Spyridon Bakas

Indiana University School of Medicine

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Florian Kofler, PhD

Hertie AI institute for brain health, University of Tübingen

florian.kofler@tum.de

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Expert clinicians under the supervision of Benedikt Wiestler (TUM) verified and corrected all healthy-tissue annotations. Furthermore, they ensured that the design of the challenge is closely aligned with real-world clinical needs.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline.

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Synapse.org

Following our successful collaboration with the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks) since the RSNA-ASNR-MICCAI BraTS 2021 challenge, we have coordinated with them and following the support from NCI (represented by Dr Keyvan Farahani in the organizing committee - Chair of the NCI AI Challenges Working Group) Synapse will be used as the platform to drive the evaluation of this cluster of challenges.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS 2026 challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in a number of ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long-time co-organizer of BraTS challenges and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC). All aforementioned NCI platforms are implemented on the Google Cloud Platform. This collaboration with Synapse, enabled by NCI/NIH support through ITCR grant (Synapse, PI) and other NCI resources represents a major advancement in the challenge design and leveraging of public resources.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026> - (Website will be publicly visible after the challenge approval)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

We are seeking the development of automated algorithms.

Participants must submit a fully automated container that no user interaction is required for successful execution.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples), as long as it does not involve resources unavailable to other participants. Example of such resources are: proprietary software, clinical expertise to create additional reference standard annotations.

Our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods. Thus, if participants have a solution that includes any resources unavailable to other participants, they are allowed to submit it, but if they do so, they **MUST** also submit a solution that does not include these resources and discuss the potential difference in their results between the two solutions.

We urge participants to coordinate with the organizers if there is any clarification required.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

All participants are allowed to use publicly available pre-trained models (e.g., foundation models), as well as additional data from datasets publicly available at the time of the challenge launch.

Since our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods, participating teams are allowed to even use data from their own institutions (unavailable to other participants) for further complementing the data, but if they do so, they **MUST** also discuss the potential difference in their results before and after using these “private” data.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but organizers and their immediate groups cannot be 1) eligible for awards, 2) announced as the winners of the challenge, or 3) included in the announced formal rankings. They will however be evaluated and if they are within the top-ranked ones they will be honorarily mentioned to contribute back to the community. Since organizing institutions are large, other employees from other labs/departments may participate and should be eligible for the awards and to be listed in the official leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge organizers are in communication with industrial partners and MICCAI SIGs, to sponsor monetary awards for the top 3 teams. Formal confirmation can only be provided after the acceptance of the challenge. Note that the organizers have been securing monetary awards during each of BraTS 2018-2025. NIH will also provide Certificates of Merit to the top 3 performing teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly at the conference and the participants will be invited to present their method during an oral presentation.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author

- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

We intend to coordinate 2 specific publication plans for BraTS 2026.

Plan 1:

Coordination of the BraTS proceedings as part of the MICCAI Satellite Event proceedings, allowing the BraTS participants to publish their methods in the associated MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings. We have already been publishing BraTS Springer proceedings since 2015. This year we will have the BraTS proceedings as part of the main MICCAI Satellite Event Springer LNCS proceedings.

Plan 2:

We coordinate a post-conference meta-analysis journal manuscript to summarize the results, findings, and insights of the 2026 challenge.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The participants are required to send the output of their methods to the evaluation platform for the scoring to occur during the training and the validation phases. At the end of the validation phase the participants are asked to identify the method they would like to evaluate in the final testing/ranking phase.

The organizers will then confirm receiving the containerized method and will evaluate it in the hidden testing data. The participants will be provided guidelines on the form of the container as we have done in previous years. This will enable confirmation of reproducibility.

During the training and validation phases, the participants will have the chance to test the functionality of their submission through both the implementation of the evaluation metrics (provided at the challenge website), as well as via the online evaluation platform (Synapse).

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We intend to publicly release the training and the validation sets, as soon as the challenge is approved but not later than April 2026, allowing participants to train and tune their methods. The validation data ground truth will not be provided to the participants, but multiple submissions to the online evaluation platform will be allowed for the validation phase. However, only 2 submissions will be allowed in the final testing/ranking data/phase to avoid potential tuning of the submitted approach to the testing data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration dates: From website opening until submission deadline of short papers reporting method and preliminary results (see below).

16 March 2026 (or earlier): Registration opens – Release of Training and Validation data

Participants will be able to register for the challenge in synapse.org, from the date of its potential acceptance (either Feb 9, or Mar 16, 2026) until the short paper submission deadline (July 31, 2026).

Availability of training data (with ground truth labels) and validation data (without ground truth labels).

15 July 2026: Submission deadline for Paper and Containerized method

Paper should include motivation, literature, method description, and results on training and validation data.

The containerized method will be evaluated on the hidden testing data by the organizers, only for participants with submitted short papers. Ranking of all participating methods, following statistical significance assessment based on multiple permutation testing.

23 July 2026: Initial invitations are sent

Inviting participants with a valid submitted paper and an evaluated container to present at the conference (type of presentation will be determined within the next 2 weeks)

7 August 2026: Paper reviews are available

19 August 2026: Release of summary testing results to each participant.

Participants will receive summary testing data results, in order to report those in their papers.

21 August 2026: Camera-ready paper and Copyright form submission deadline

24 August 2026: Contacting top-performing methods for preparing slides for oral presentation.

1 September 2026: Organizers to send all proceedings material to the MICCAI 2026 Satellite Event committee for inclusion in the MICCAI LNCS Springer Proceedings.

4-8 October 2026: Challenge at MICCAI

Announcement of final top 3 ranked teams

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The inpainting challenge operates on data from the BraTS segmentation challenges (adult glioma + meningioma). Therefore, the respective ethics approvals apply.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

The inpainting challenge operates on data from the BraTS segmentation challenges (adult glioma + meningioma). Therefore, the respective licenses apply.

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The implementation and references to the pre-processing tools, exact evaluation metrics, and the ranking code used during the whole challenge's lifecycle will be made available through the challenge's website (<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants are required to submit their containerized algorithm, during or after the validation phase. Specific instructions for the containerization will be provided after the challenge approval. These instructions will be very similar to what we were requesting participants to provide during the BraTS 2021-2025 challenges.

All challenge participants will be required to accept an agreement through the synapse.org website that participation in the testing phase of the challenge, will automatically mean that we can make their containerized method publicly available through our challenge webpage and a collective toolkit we are putting together.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in several ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long time co-organizer of BraTS challenges and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of

an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC) on the Google Cloud Platform

The organizers are in coordination with industrial collaborators to offer dissemination of top-ranked containerized methods for research use only, through their commercial platforms, subject to participating teams accepting this opportunity.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Spyridon Bakas and SAGE Bionetworks (synapse.org) are the only ones who will have access to the validation, and test case ground truth labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Decision support, Treatment planning, Intervention planning, Education, Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Inpainting, Infilling, Image Synthesis

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients, diagnosed with brain tumors. We hope that, due to the lesion-agnostic challenge design, the resulting inpainting algorithms can be used to inpaint all kinds of brain lesions and scanner artifacts.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Retrospective multi-institutional cohorts of patients from the BraTS segmentation challenges (adult glioma + meningioma)

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

T1-weighted MR sequences from the BraTS segmentation challenges.

Even though the segmentation challenges acquired 4 multi-parametric MRI sequences.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information pertains directly to the image data (i.e., Tumor sub-region labels and volumes)

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

N/A

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

BraTS segmentation challenges (adult glioma + meningioma)

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patients with brain tumors, scanned with clinically routine MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

PSNR,MSE,SSIM

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The exact scanners and their technical specifications used for acquiring the data used in this challenge span across multiple institutions and acquisition protocols published in the BraTS glioma and meningioma related manuscripts, as well as in the TCIA data collections for each sequence separately.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The acquisition protocols are different across (and within each) contributing institution, as these represent scans of real routine clinical practice. Specific details (e.g., echo time, repetition time, original acquisition plane) of each scan of each patient will be published as supplementary material together with the challenge meta-analysis manuscript.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The provided data describe mpMRI scans, acquired with different clinical protocols and various scanners from the adult glioma segmentation task of BraTS 2021-2022.

University of Pennsylvania (PA, USA), University of Alabama at Birmingham (AL, USA), Heidelberg University (Germany), University of Bern (Switzerland), University of Debrecen (Hungary), Henry Ford Hospital (MI, USA), University of California (CA, USA), MD Anderson Cancer Center (TX, USA), Emory University (GA, USA), Mayo Clinic (MN, USA), Thomas Jefferson University (PA, USA), Duke University School of Medicine (NC, USA), Saint Joseph Hospital and Medical Center (AZ, USA), Case Western Reserve University (OH, USA), University of North Carolina (NC, USA), Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Neurologico C. Besta, (Italy), Ivy Glioblastoma Atlas Project, MD Anderson Cancer Center (TX, USA), Washington University in St. Louis (MO, USA), Tata Memorial Center (India), University of Pittsburg Medical Center (PA, USA), University of California San Francisco (CA, USA), Unity Health, University Hospital of Zurich.

For the meningioma segmentation task the provided data describe MRI scans from the BraTS 2023 Meningioma challenge, acquired with different clinical protocols and various scanners from: Duke University, University of Pennsylvania, Missouri University, University of California San Francisco, Yale University, Thomas Jefferson University

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Clinical staff involved in MRI acquisition for suspected and diagnosed brain tumor patients during standard clinical practice.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

For the segmentation challenges a case describes multi-parametric MRI scans for a single patient at a single timepoint. The exact scans included for one case are i) unenhanced and ii) contrast-enhanced T1-weighted, iii) T2-weighted and iv) T2 Fluid Attenuated Inversion Recovery (FLAIR) MRI.

Please note that all sequences included for each case of the provided dataset, represent the sequences with the best image quality available in the acquiring institution for this particular case. There was no inclusion/exclusion criterion applied that related to 3d acquisitions, or the exact type of pulse sequence (for example MPRAGE). We, instead, accepted all types of T1 acquisitions (with the exception of T1 FLAIR, as we did not want to mix the fluid suppressed values with non-flair scans) and then we applied the harmonized preprocessing protocol we have

been using in BraTS, across the complete data. This preprocessing ensures all scans have 3D representations on a specific resolution (1mm^3), and aligned to the same anatomical atlas.

While all modalities are used to generate the segmentation labels, the inpainting challenge now only takes the T1 pre-contrast scan from a segmentation case and provides labels for healthy and unhealthy brain; the unhealthy brain label is obtained by merging the tumor segmentations, while the healthy brain is obtained via the public sampling algorithm - please also see the section below.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training data: 1251 cases;

Validation data: 219 cases;

Testing data glioma: $570-2 = 568$ (two excluded) cases

Testing data meningioma : $284-7=277$ (seven excluded) cases

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data that should be annotated are already annotated. No further annotation efforts are needed for this year's challenge.

As mentioned in the initial novelty section, we will also be offering to the participants non-annotated cases to facilitate innovations in semi-supervised learning approaches.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Based on availability. All available data were split into training, validation, and testing following a 70%-10%-20% proportion, in line with conventional proportions used in machine learning studies.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

For the local inpainting task, only the T1 sequence is used, and we provide two types of masks: tumor (unhealthy) masks and healthy masks. The tumor masks specify the regions affected by the tumor that require inpainting, while the healthy masks cover regions of the healthy brain with similar size and shape. Since there is no ground truth available for the true appearance of the tumor regions, we cannot directly evaluate the quality of inpainting in these areas. The healthy masks allow us to compute evaluation metrics in regions with known structure, providing a reliable baseline for assessing the inpainting performance.

During training, both types of masks are available to enable supervised learning. This allows algorithms to learn how to inpaint both tumor-affected and healthy regions, improving their capacity to reconstruct plausible brain structures.

In the testing phase, the focus is solely on evaluating the quality of inpainting in the healthy brain areas. All image intensities inside the inpainting regions will be set to a predefined value, and only the reconstruction of healthy areas will be used to evaluate the algorithm's performance.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All test data are fully unseen, and, therefore, constitute a "true" test set.

No new annotated data will be provided in this year's challenge.

The testing data has always remained unseen and not published.

New data used in this year's challenge describe non-annotated cases to enable innovation in semi-supervised approaches.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The tumor segmentations were derived from the BraTS segmentation challenges.

Healthy evaluation regions were created through our publicly available sampling algorithm and then verified by a medical domain expert as described in detail in our challenge manuscript. Borderline cases were decided in consensus voting with further domain experts.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The BraTS glioma segmentation labels follow the following instructions:

Key annotation of all BRATS image data sets is the tumor annotation for this task.

The tumor image annotation follows the paradigm of the BraTS 2021 challenge data. The annotation of these data followed a pre-defined clinically-approved annotation protocol (defined by expert neuroradiologists), which was provided to all clinical annotators, describing in detail instructions on what the segmentations of each tumor subregion should describe (see below for the summary of the specific instructions). The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations, and also follow either a complete manual annotation approach, or a hybrid approach where an automated approach is used to produce some initial annotations followed by their manual refinements.

Summary of specific instructions:

the enhancing tumor (when present) delineates the hyperintense signal of the T1-Gd, after excluding the vessels. the necrotic core (when present) outlines regions appearing dark in both T1 and T1-Gd images (denoting necrosis/cysts), and darked regions in T1-Gd that appear brighter in T1. iii) the tumor core, which is the union of the enhancing tumor and the necrotic core described in (i) and (ii) above. iv) the farthest tumor extent including the edema (what is called the whole tumor), delineates the tissue represented by the abnormal T2-FLAIR envelope.

These glioma segmentations serve as input for our algorithm (see above) and are then curated by trained experts to make sure they do not contain other pathologies. The medical domain experts were proposed with several sample regions and selected the best candidates in an iterative process. Some patients had to be excluded from the test sets as the domain experts could not find healthy brain due to comorbidities. For more details please

refer to our challenge manuscript.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each case was assigned to a pair of annotator-approver. Annotators spanned across various experience levels and clinical/academic ranks, while the approvers were the 2 experienced board-certified neuroradiologists (with >15 years of experience), listed in the Organizers section as clinical evaluators and annotation approvers. The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations, and also follow either a complete manual annotation approach, or a hybrid approach where an automated approach is used to produce some initial annotations followed by their manual refinements. Once the annotators were satisfied with the produced annotations, they were passing these to the corresponding approver. The approver is then responsible for signing off these annotations. Specifically, the approver would review the tumor annotations, in tandem with the corresponding MRI scans, and if the annotations were not of satisfactory quality they would be sent back to the annotators for further refinements. This iterative approach was followed for all cases, until their respective annotations reached satisfactory quality (according to the approver) for being publicly available and noted as final ground truth segmentation labels for these scans.

For the inpainting challenge, we designed an algorithm that samples inpainting masks in the healthy brain area. These areas are similar in size and shape to tumor areas. The code for obtaining these is publicly available: https://github.com/BraTS-inpainting/2025_challenge/blob/main/dataset/dataset_generation.ipynb

The resulting areas were done by medical domain expert underwent medical training and has several years of experience. Edge cases were discussed with several domain experts in consensus voting.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No Aggregation.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The exact preprocessing pipeline applied to all the data considered in the BraTS 2026 challenge is identical with the one evaluated and followed by the BraTS 2017-2025 challenges. Specifically, following the conversion of the raw scans from their original DICOM file format to NIfTI file format, we first perform a re-orientation of all input scans (T1, T1- Gd, T2, T2-FLAIR) to the LPS/RAI orientation, and then register all of them to the same anatomical atlas (i.e., SRI-24) and interpolating to the same resolution as this atlas (1 mm³). The exact registration process comprises the following steps:

STEP 1: N4 Bias field correction (notably the application of N4 bias field correction is a temporary step. Taking into consideration we have previously shown that the use of non-parametric, non-uniform intensity normalization (i.e., N4) to correct for intensity non-uniformities caused by the inhomogeneity of the scanners magnetic field during image acquisition obliterates the MRI signal relating to the abnormal/tumor regions, we intentionally use N4 bias field correction in the preprocessing pipeline to facilitate a more optimal rigid registration across the difference

MRI sequences. However, after obtaining the related information (i.e., transformation matrices), we discard the bias field corrected scans, and we apply this transformation matrix towards the final co-registered output images used in the challenge).

STEP 2: Rigid Registration of T1, T2, T2-FLAIR to the T1-Gd scan, and obtain the corresponding transformation matrix.

STEP 3: Rigid Registration of T1-Gd scan to the SRI-24 atlas, and obtain the corresponding transformation matrix.

STEP 4: Join the obtained transformation matrices and applying aggregated transformation to the LPS-oriented scans.

STEP 5: After completion of the registration process, we perform brain extraction to remove any apparent nonbrain tissue (e.g., neck fat, skull, eyeballs) based on a deep-learning approach we developed in house, focusing on scans with apparent brain tumors and exhaustively evaluated it in both private and public multi-institutional data. We then manually assessed all scans for confirming the correct brain extraction (i.e., skull stripping), where the complete brain region is included, and all non-brain tissue is excluded.

This whole pipeline, and its source code are available through the CaPTk (<https://github.com/CBICA/CaPTk>) and FeTS (<https://fets-ai.github.io/Front-End/>) platforms.

Step 6: Run the inpainting dataset generation tool, available here:

https://github.com/BraTS-inpainting/2023_challenge/blob/main/dataset/dataset_generation.ipynb

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Study and evaluation of the effect of this error is addressed by the uncertainty task of BraTS 2019-2020 (i.e., to quantify the uncertainty in the tumor segmentations) and is outside the scope of the BraTS 2025 Glioma challenge.

R.Mehta, et al, QU-BraTS: MICCAI BraTS 2020 Challenge on Quantifying Uncertainty in Brain Tumor Segmentation-Analysis of Ranking Scores and Benchmarking Results, Journal of Machine Learning for Biomedical Imaging, 1, 26, 2022

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The Structural similarity Index (SSIM) is used to evaluate the quality of brain structures in synthetic images, i.e. to compare synthetic sequences with their physically acquired counterparts, as does the L2 norm distance and Peak Signal to noise ratio (PSNR).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

We choose the three most popular metrics to evaluate image synthesis methods:

- RMSE (root mean square error)
- PSNR (Peak Signal to Noise Ratio)
- Structural similarity index (SSIM) which is commonly perceptual metric to quantify image similarity between synthetic images and reference images.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

As the metrics work on different scales we want to aggregate in scale-agnostic fashion. Further, we want to assign equal weight to all cases. The ranking scheme was developed in collaboration with Dr. Annika Reinke (DKFZ).

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, we set the scores to the worst possible rank for this case.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

To measure the performance of the contributions, we will evaluate the quality of the infilled regions. Since ground truth data is only available for the masked regions with healthy tissue, the evaluation will be restricted to these.

We will use the following set of well-established metrics to quantify how realistic the synthesized image regions are compared to real ones: structural similarity index measure (SSIM), peak-signal-to-noise-ratio, and mean-square-error (MSE). For the final ranking of the MICCAI challenge, an equally weighted rank-sum is computed across all three metrics. To compute the rank within each metric, we rank the participants for each case and again compute a rank-sum. For these computations we use the publicly available challengeR: <https://github.com/wiesenfa/challengeR>

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Statistical analyses for the BraTS inpainting challenge follow the established BraTS 2017–2025 protocol and rely on non-parametric, case-level resampling in R using the challengeR package. We use 1000-fold bootstrap and permutation-based analyses to estimate uncertainty and robustness of metrics and rankings because they do not

assume normality and are suitable for skewed or heavy-tailed performance distributions. Descriptive statistics and distributional visualizations summarize per-case performance and help inspect basic assumptions, while rank-based methods such as Kendall's Tau are used because rankings are ordinal and sensitive to outliers, and all resampling is done at the test-case level to respect independence of observations.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Similar to BraTS 2017-2025, uncertainties and robustness of rankings will be assessed using permutational analyses. Therefore, as in 2023-2025, we conduct 1000-fold bootstrapping and robustness analysis with challengeR.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD and IQR across test cases – visualized as violin plots in our meta-analysis article and presented at the time of the challenge. Furthermore, we report the mean, standard errors and outliers.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Using 1000-fold bootstrapping we compute a ranking robustness analysis (see above).

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

We compute Kendall's Tau. Furthermore we exploit challengeR's capabilities to visualize rank differences using podium plots, ranking heatmaps and significance.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

N/A, as if an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, we set the scores to the worst possible rank for this case.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Statistical computations happen in R using the publicly available challengeR:
<https://github.com/wiesenfa/challengeR>

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

In addition to the challenge metrics we will also evaluate perceptual metrics such as LPIPS and provide qualitative expert evaluations. Furthermore, we will experiment with a new metrics assessing grey- and white matter anatomy segmentation performance.

For this novel metric, which we designed to capture the actual clinical/anatomical fidelity of the image

reconstruction, we perform tissue segmentation on the inpainted brains and compare the resulting GM/WM/CSF segmentation masks to the tissue segmentation maps from the reference brains. This analysis will be limited to the healthy tissue regions and for this comparison we will employ typical segmentation metrics, such as DSC and NSD.

TASK 5: BraTS-Pathology: Classification of brain glioblastoma sub-regions in H&E-stained; pathology slides

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Glioblastoma is the most common primary adult-type diffuse tumor of the brain, with a very grim prognosis (median survival of 15 months). Glioblastoma is widely infiltrative in the cerebral hemispheres and well-known for its vastly heterogenous molecular profiles and histopathologic/morphologic landscape. A major obstacle in treating these tumors is this micro-environmental heterogeneity. Correctly diagnosing these tumors and assessing their heterogeneity is crucial for choosing the precise treatment and potentially enhancing patient survival rates. In the reference standard histopathology-based approach to tumor diagnosis, detecting various morpho-pathological features of distinct histology throughout digitized tissue sections is crucial. Such "features" include the presence of cellular tumor, geographic necrosis, pseudopalisading necrosis, areas abundant in microvascular proliferation, infiltration into the cortex, wide extension in subcortical white matter, leptomeningeal infiltration, regions dense with macrophages, and the presence of perivascular or scattered lymphocytes.

With these features in mind and building upon the main aim of the BraTS Cluster of Challenges, the goal of the BraTS-Pathology challenge is to seek the development of computational algorithms capable of identifying tumor sub-regions of distinct histologic profile. These algorithms aim to assist in the diagnosis and grading of conditions in a consistent manner. In the BraTS-Pathology challenge dataset, we focus on glioblastoma digitized tissue sections with representative features. In partnership with the RANO-Pathology group, an international team of neuropathologists annotated H&E-stained; slides, by identifying these distinct sub-regions. Subsequently, these sub-regions were partitioned into patches classified based on the presence of specific histology. This approach established a classification task aimed at accurately identifying patches with specific features. The challenge participants can obtain the labeled training data at any point from the Synapse platform. These data will be used to develop, containerize, and evaluate their algorithms in unseen validation data until July 2026, when the organizers will stop accepting new submissions and evaluate the submitted algorithms in the hidden testing data. Ground truth reference annotations for all datasets are created and approved by expert neuropathologists for every subject included in the training, validation, and testing datasets to evaluate the performance of the participating algorithms quantitatively.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Classification, Pathology, Brain, Tumor, Glioblastoma, Digital Pathology, Computational Pathology, Cancer, Challenge, Glioma, MICCAI, RANO, diffuse glioma

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Suhang (Jayden) You [1,2], Siddhesh P. Thakur [1,2], Carla Pitarch-Abaigar [1,2], Verena Chung [3], MacLean P. Nasrallah [4], Jared T. Ahrendsen [5], Valeria Barresi [6], Maria A. Gubbiotti [7], Giselle Y. Lopez [8,9], Calixto-Hope G. Lucas [10], Michael L. Miller [11], Ujjwal Baid [12], Gian Marco Conte [13], Dominic LaBella [14], Benedikt Wiestler [15], Bjoern Menze [16], Maria Correia de Verdier [17], Raymond Huang [18], Jeff Rudie [19], Zhifan Jiang [20], Marius George Linguraru [20,21], Mehdi Astaraki [22], Alexandros Karargyris [23], Hasan Kassem [23], Keyvan Farahani [24], Lee A. D. Cooper [5], Martin van den Bent [25], Timothy Cloughesy [26], Michael A. Vogelbaum [27], Patrick Y. Wen [28], Susan Chang [29], William R. Bell [1,2], Jason T. Huse [7,30], Spyridon Bakas [1,2,23,31,32,33]

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18 Department of Radiology, Brigham and Woman's Hospital, Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, USA

19 Department of Radiology, University of California, San Diego CA, USA

20 Sheikh Zayed Institute for Pediatric Surgical Innovation, Children's National Hospital, Washington, DC, USA

21 Departments of Radiology and Pediatrics, The George Washington University, Washington, DC, USA

22 Karolinska Institute

23 Medical Research Group, MLCcommons, San Francisco, CA, USA

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b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Spyridon Bakas, PhD

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c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes. Roles included 1) ensuring and increasing clinical relevance, 2) generation of annotations, 3) definition of annotation protocol, 4) review of reference standard, 5) interpretation of results.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline, and continuous evaluation after the conference deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

Synapse.org

Following our successful collaboration with the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks) since the RSNA-ASNR-MICCAI BraTS 2021 challenge, we have coordinated with them and following the support from NCI (represented by Dr Keyvan Farahani in the organizing committee - Chair of the NCI AI Challenges Working Group) Synapse will be used as the platform to drive the evaluation of this cluster of challenges.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS 2026 challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in a number of ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long-time co-organizer of BraTS challenges and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC). All aforementioned NCI platforms are implemented on the Google Cloud Platform. This collaboration with Synapse, enabled by NCI/NIH support through ITCR grant (Synapse, PI) and other NCI resources represents a major advancement in the challenge design and leveraging of public resources.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026> - (Website will be publicly visible after the challenge approval)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

We are seeking the development of automated algorithms.

Participants must submit a fully automated container that no user interaction is required for successful execution.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding some training samples), as long as it does not involve resources unavailable to other participants. Example of such resources are: proprietary software, clinical expertise to create additional reference standard annotations.

Our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods. Thus, if participants have a solution that includes any resources unavailable to other participants, they are allowed to submit it, but if they do so, they **MUST** also submit a solution that does not include these resources and discuss the potential difference in their results between the two solutions.

We urge participants to coordinate with the organizers if there is any clarification required.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding

(private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

All participants are allowed to use publicly available pre-trained models (e.g., foundation models), as well as additional data from datasets publicly available at the time of the challenge launch.

Since our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods, participating teams are allowed to even use data from their own institutions (unavailable to other participants) for further complementing the data, but if they do so, they MUST also discuss the potential difference in their results before and after using these “private” data.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but organizers and their immediate groups cannot be 1) eligible for awards, 2) announced as the winners of the challenge, or 3) included in the announced formal rankings. They will however be evaluated and if they are within the top-ranked ones they will be honorarily mentioned to contribute back to the community. Since organizing institutions are large, other employees from other labs/departments may participate and should be eligible for the awards and to be listed in the official leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The challenge organizers are in communication with industrial partners and MICCAI SIGs, to sponsor monetary awards for the top 3 teams. Formal confirmation can only be provided after the acceptance of the challenge. Note that the organizers have been securing monetary awards during each of BraTS 2018-2025. NIH will also provide Certificates of Merit to the top 3 performing teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly at the conference and the participants will be invited to present their method during an oral presentation.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

We intend to coordinate 2 specific publication plans for BraTS 2026.

Plan 1:

Coordination of the BraTS proceedings as part of the MICCAI Satellite Event proceedings, allowing the BraTS participants to publish their methods in the associated MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings. We have already been publishing BraTS Springer proceedings since 2015. This year we will have the BraTS proceedings as part of the main MICCAI Satellite Event Springer LNCS proceedings.

Plan 2:

We coordinate a post-conference meta-analysis journal manuscript to summarize the results, findings, and insights of the 2026 challenge.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The participants are required to send the output of their methods to the evaluation platform for the scoring to occur during the training and the validation phases. At the end of the validation phase the participants are asked to identify the method they would like to evaluate in the final testing/ranking phase.

The organizers will then confirm receiving the containerized method and will evaluate it in the hidden testing data. The participants will be provided guidelines on the form of the container as we have done in previous years. This will enable confirmation of reproducibility.

During the training and validation phases, the participants will have the chance to test the functionality of their submission through both the implementation of the evaluation metrics (provided at the challenge website), as well as via the online evaluation platform (Synapse).

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We intend to publicly release the training and the validation sets, as soon as the challenge is approved but not later than April 2026, allowing participants to train and tune their methods. The validation data ground truth will not be provided to the participants, but multiple submissions to the online evaluation platform will be allowed for the validation phase. However, only 2 submissions will be allowed in the final testing/ranking data/phase to avoid potential tuning of the submitted approach to the testing data.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Registration dates: From website opening until submission deadline of short papers reporting method and preliminary results (see below).

16 March 2026 (or earlier): Registration opens – Release of Training and Validation data

Participants will be able to register for the challenge in synapse.org, from the date of its potential acceptance (either Feb 9, or Mar 16, 2026) until the short paper submission deadline (July 31, 2026).

Availability of training data (with ground truth labels) and validation data (without ground truth labels).

31 July 2026: Submission deadline for Paper and Containerized method

Paper should include motivation, literature, method description, and results on training and validation data.

The containerized method will be evaluated on the hidden testing data by the organizers, only for participants with submitted short papers. Ranking of all participating methods, following statistical significance assessment based on multiple permutation testing.

7 August 2026: Initial invitations are sent

Inviting participants with a valid submitted paper and an evaluated container to present at the conference (type of presentation will be determined within the next 2 weeks)

14 August 2026: Paper reviews are available

19 August 2026: Release of summary testing results to each participant.

Participants will receive summary testing data results, in order to report those in their papers.

21 August 2026: Camera-ready paper and Copyright form submission deadline

24 August 2026: Contacting top-performing methods for preparing slides for oral presentation.

1 September 2026: Organizers to send all proceedings material to the MICCAI 2026 Satellite Event committee for inclusion in the MICCAI LNCS Springer Proceedings.

4-8 October 2026: Challenge at MICCAI

Announcement of final top 3 ranked teams

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

Not applicable, as these cases are already publicly available from The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA), as part of the TCGA-GBM and TCGA-LGG data collections. However, please note that expert clinicians at our end worked on their reclassification according to the latest WHO classification criteria.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY (Attribution)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The implementation and references to the pre-processing tools, exact evaluation metrics, and the ranking code used during the whole challenge's lifecycle will be made available through the challenge's website (<https://www.synapse.org/brats2026>).

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants are required to submit their containerized algorithm, during or after the validation phase. Specific instructions for the containerization will be provided after the challenge approval. These instructions will be very similar to what we were requesting participants to provide during the BraTS 2021-2025 challenges.

All challenge participants will be required to accept an agreement through the synapse.org website that participation in the testing phase of the challenge, will automatically mean that we can make their containerized method publicly available through our challenge webpage and a collective toolkit we are putting together.

The National Cancer Institute takes special interest in the BraTS challenge and is considering providing infrastructural support in several ways. Dr Keyvan Farahani, a long time co-organizer of BraTS challenges and a project scientist on a collaborative NCI Informatics Technology for Cancer Research (ITCR) grant, is the recipient of an NIH Office of Data Science and Strategy (ODSS)-STRIDES award for a sustainable medical imaging challenge cloud infrastructure, to further implement open (continuous) challenges by supporting cloud compute and other infrastructures for (a) benchmarking of tools and automated submission of containerized tools for evaluation, (b) hosting of top-ranking tools through NCI FireCloud Resource and public tool repository such as Dockstore or ModelHub, and (c) hosting resulting image annotations as derived data in the Imaging Data Commons (IDC) on the Google Cloud Platform

The organizers are in coordination with industrial collaborators to offer dissemination of top-ranked

containerized methods for research use only, through their commercial platforms, subject to participating teams accepting this opportunity.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

Spyridon Bakas, Jayden You, Siddhesh Thakur, and SAGE Bionetworks (synapse.org), will be the only ones who will have access to the validation, and test case ground truth labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis,Prognosis,Research,Treatment planning,CAD,Decision support,Assistance,Intervention planning,Education,Training

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction

- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Patients, diagnosed with de novo adult-type diffuse glioma of the brain.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Retrospective multi-institutional cohort of patients, diagnosed with de novo adult-type diffuse glioma of the brain, with clinically digitized tissue sections using the paradigm of Formalin-Fixed Paraffin-Embedded (FFPE) and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E);.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Histopathology images. Specifically, H&E-stained; FFPE digitized tissue sections.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information pertains directly to the image data (i.e., Tumor sub-region class)

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

N/A

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain tumor tissue showing in H&E-stained; FFPE digitized tissue sections.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Patches of H&E-stained; digitized tissue sections of adult-type diffuse glioma.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Sensitivity, Specificity, AUC, Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), F1 Score

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The H&E-stained; FFPE digitized tissue sections used in the BraTS-Path challenge, describe histology images acquired during standard clinical practice across the 11 International sites mentioned in (c) below. The exact staining process details and the digital scanners (with their technical specifications) used for acquiring this TCIA cohort are not publicly available neither through TCIA, nor through the Genomic Data Commons (GDC) Data Portal of the NIH/NCI.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The exact staining process details and the digital scanners (with their technical specifications) used across these 11 sites to acquire this TCIA cohort are not publicly available neither through TCIA, nor through the Genomic Data Commons (GDC) Data Portal of the NIH/NCI. We appreciate that the acquisition protocols and equipment are different across (and within each) contributing institution, as these represent real routine clinical practice. We are in coordination with TCIA to identify as much of these specific details for each image of each patient and then publish this as supplementary material together with the challenge meta-analysis manuscript. The collected WSI were scanned at two magnifications: 20x (0.2457–0.2533 mpp) and 40x (0.4993–0.5040 mpp).

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The provided data describe H&E-stained; FFPE digitized tissue sections, acquired with different clinical protocols and various scanners from:

- 1) Henry Ford Hospital (MI, USA),

- 2) University of California (CA, USA),
- 3) MD Anderson Cancer Center (TX, USA),
- 4) Emory University (GA, USA),
- 5) Mayo Clinic (MN, USA),
- 6) Thomas Jefferson University (PA, USA),
- 7) Duke University School of Medicine (NC, USA),
- 8) Saint Joseph Hospital and Medical Center (AZ, USA),
- 9) Case Western Reserve University (OH, USA),
- 10) University of North Carolina (NC, USA),
- 11) Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Neurologico C. Besta, (Italy),

Note that data from these institutions are provided through The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA <http://www.cancerimagingarchive.net/>), supported by the Cancer Imaging Program (CIP) of the National Cancer Institute (NCI) of the National Institutes of Health (NIH).

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Clinical experts (neuropathologists and technicians) involved in tissue staining for suspected and diagnosed brain tumor patients during standard clinical practice.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Based on the given definition (in this section - (a)) that a case encompasses data processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result, a case in this challenge represents an individual patch extracted from an H&E-stained; FFPE digitized tissue section of a single patient tumor at a specific timepoint.

We ensure that the patches are of a similar size, with each representing either a specific class present in that patch or none, in which case it was classified as 'background'. These tissue sections exhibit a variety of features indicative of the diagnosis of a glioblastoma and have been annotated by expert neuropathologists. These annotated regions are divided into same size patches, each of them corresponding to a distinct morpho-histologic feature/class that the participants are expected to predict. Since this task has not been conducted before, we consider individual patches as individual cases in this challenge, with the intention of conducting a deeper analysis and offer a deeper understanding of these distinct features/classes in a more fine-grained resolution.

Specifically, we would like to assess the intrinsic similarity of these classes and hence inherent difficulty of detecting individual classes, as well as which are the most confused with each other features/classes. Throughout both the training, validation, and testing phases, these patches are classified according to their respective features/classes. The inclusion criteria for each tissue section were determined by the presence of histologic features characteristic of glioblastoma. Please note that all tissue sections included for each case of the provided dataset, represent the tissue sections with the best quality available for this particular case.

The data are split across the training, validation and testing sets following a patient-level separation, to avoid information leakage that might occur during training and inference.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training cases: 749,269.

Validation cases: 298,532.

Testing cases: 1,177,508.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All data that should be annotated are already annotated. No further annotation efforts are needed for this year's challenge.

As mentioned in the initial novelty section, we will also be offering to the participants non-annotated cases to facilitate innovations in semi-supervised learning approaches.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Based on availability, and while keeping in mind good machine learning practices.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution. Choice was made to ensure methods that can consider the challenging real-world problem and extend to a more difficult task in the next year, including recurring glioma.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

No new annotated data will be provided in this year's challenge.

The testing data has always remained unseen and not published.

New data used in this year's challenge describe non-annotated cases to enable innovation in semi-supervised approaches.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Reference approved or edited until consensus from 2 experienced neuropathologists, following manual annotations from 16 clinical neuropathologists (volunteers from the RANO cooperative group).

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotation of these data followed a pre-defined clinically-approved annotation protocol (defined by expert neuropathologists), which was provided to all clinical annotators, describing in detail instructions on what the segmentations of each histologic feature should describe (see below for the summary of the specific instructions). The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations, or the provided infrastructure based on the Digital Slide Archive available through a web portal by Indiana University, and follow a complete manual annotation approach.

Summary of specific histologic areas of interest: (with annotated number of patches in train, validation and test split)

- i) presence of cellular tumor (250,370; 85,903; 355,502)
- ii) pseudopalisading necrosis (38,821; 2,773; 41,163)
- iii) areas abundant in microvascular proliferation (21,349; 221, 158,094)
- iv) geographic necrosis (259,329; 88,821; 152,019)
- v) infiltration into the cortex (126,773; 58,735; 330,519)
- vi) penetration into white matter (39,851; 56,067; 136,796)
- vii) leptomenigeal infiltration (6,419; 4,663; 1,738)
- viii) regions dense with macrophages (4,359; 556; 877)
- ix) presence of lymphocytes (1,998; 793; 800)

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Each case was assigned to a pair of annotator-approver. Annotators spanned across various experience levels and clinical/academic ranks, while the approvers were the 2 experienced board-certified neuropathologists (with >10 years of experience), listed in the Organizers' section as Clinical Organizers. The annotators were given the flexibility to use their tool of preference for making the annotations, or the provided infrastructure based on the Digital Slide Archive available through a web portal by Indiana University, and follow a complete manual annotation approach. Once the annotators were satisfied with the produced annotations, they were passing these to the corresponding approver. The approver is then responsible for signing off these annotations. Specifically, the approver would review the tumor annotations, in tandem with the corresponding tissue section, and the annotations of not satisfactory quality were removed from the provided annotation. If the patches from the remaining annotations were less than approximately 1,500 patches then the tissue sections would be sent back to the annotators for further annotations. This iterative approach was followed for all cases, until their respective annotations reached satisfactory quality (according to the approver) for being publicly available and noted as final ground truth segmentation labels for these cases.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No Aggregation.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The TCGA-GBM and TCGA-LGG data sets, which are publicly accessible via the TCIA, have been chosen for this challenge. Initially, we have reclassified these collections in line with the 2021 WHO classification of CNS tumors. This reclassification was specifically done to pinpoint all cases of GBM IDH-wildtype, CNS WHO Grade 4. The TCGA-LGG collection subjects, initially classified as low-grade astrocytomas, are redefined under the 2021 WHO CNS criteria as GBM if they are IDH-wildtype. This enables algorithmic development applicable to all clinical GBM as per the most updated WHO 2021 guidelines. Conversely, certain cases in the TCGA-GBM collection have been excluded because their molecular profiles do not align with the current WHO definition of GBM, IDH-mutant. For this study, multiple H&E-stained; tissue sections from each case in the reclassified TCGA-GBM and TCGA-LGG collections are used. Focusing solely on FFPE slides, we avoid hydration artifacts common in frozen sections. Post annotation of histologically distinct regions by clinical experts, each region is segmented into 512x512 patches. No patch-level image curation is essential as annotations are created carefully on areas of high confidence for clear appearance content.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

N/A, as only areas of high confidence from at least 2 neuro-pathologists are used for the patch creation. Perhaps at a later version of the challenge we could propose to study and evaluate the effect of any potential annotations error as an uncertainty task, similar to the one we did in BraTS 2019-2020 (i.e., to quantify the uncertainty in the tumor segmentations), but for now this is outside the scope of the BraTS-Path 2026 challenge.

R.Mehta, et al, QU-BraTS: MICCAI BraTS 2020 Challenge on Quantifying Uncertainty in Brain Tumor Segmentation-Analysis of Ranking Scores and Benchmarking Results, Journal of Machine Learning Biomedical Imaging, 1, 26, 2022.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Accuracy,

AUC,

F1 Score,

Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC),

Sensitivity,
Specificity.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

In terms of evaluation metrics, we use:

I) Accuracy will provide the proportion of true results (both true positives and true negatives) among the total number of cases examined. It proves the effectiveness of the classification model.

II) MCC provides a balanced measure even when the classes are of very different sizes. It is a correlation coefficient between the observed and predicted classifications, offering a more informative and nuanced assessment than simple accuracy.

III) As a measure that balances precision and recall (sensitivity), the F1 score is crucial for scenarios where the cost of false positives and false negatives is high. It is particularly useful when dealing with imbalance between classes.

IV) AUCROC curve, quantifies the overall ability of the model to discriminate between the positive and negative classes across different thresholds. A higher AUC indicates better model performance

V) Sensitivity and Specificity to determine whether an algorithm has the tendency to over- or under-classify different classes.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

Ranking of methods will be based on the aggregate of rankings of F1 score and MCC. Specifically, we will follow the DELPHI-based recommendations for image analysis validation [1,2], incorporating i) algorithmic ranking, and ii) statistical significance testing. Building upon the approach in BraTS 2017-2025, the performance of the classification task will be evaluated based on the relative performance (as an aggregate metric of the ones described above) of each team's model in classifying different tumor tissue types. For this analysis we will divide the test data into multiple non-overlapping subsets, ensuring balanced class representation. The assessment will involve a detailed analysis of each model's classification performance for various tumor tissues. We then compute an average rank for each of the subsets across both metrics, and aggregated these average rankings to produce a conclusive overall ranking.

[1] Reinke et al. Understanding metric-related pitfalls in image analysis validation. Nat Methods. 2024 Feb;21(2):182-194.

[2] Maier-Hein et al. Metrics reloaded: recommendations for image analysis validation. Nat Methods. 2024 Feb;21(2):195-212.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, this metric will be set to its worst possible value (e.g., 0 for F1 score)

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Following discussions with the biostatistician involved in the design of this challenge (Dr Kun Huang, Chair of Dept of Biostatistics & Health Data Science), and also while considering transparency and fairness to the participants.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

We will leverage the same statistical framework we have been applying to BraTS over the last years, which provides a fair, transparent, and robust evaluation framework building upon two stages: (i) a ranking score generated for each evaluated method, based on case-wise cumulative rankings aggregated across the pre-specified metrics reported above and across unseen hold-out cases, and (ii) a rigorous statistical significance assessment, based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Compared to a simplistic ordinal ranking, this two-staged methodology provides a more holistic assessment of model performance, identifying if performance differences between any two models are statistically significant and systematic, or the result of chance on a particular test set.

The article describing in detail the exact method has been accepted and will be released as part of the MICCAI BraTS 2025 Springer LNCS proceedings.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

SD and IQR across test cases – visualized as violin plots in our meta-analysis article and presented at the time of the challenge. Furthermore, we report the mean, standard errors and outliers.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Based on pairwise permutation testing across the ranked order of the evaluated models.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

One-sided test assessment – the methodological details of the test for significance span over 2 pages of the accepted article. Springer informed us that this article should be released within March 2026.

To maintain statistical rigor, a correction for multiple comparisons, such as the Bonferroni correction or controlling the False Discovery Rate, will be applied to the p-values before interpretation.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

N/A, as if an algorithm fails to produce a result metric for a specific test case, we set the scores to the worst possible rank for this case.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

The software that we will use is released as an open-source tool through GitHub (<https://github.com/IUCompPath/PermRanker>) and we anticipate the release of its accompanying article to be available in March 2026.

We will provide pointers to the article and the software in the challenge website.
We would be happy to update the design document once the article is available.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A